

Research Article

G-D's Physics Revolutionizes Science's Basic Conception of the Universe's Origination, Development & "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State!

Jehonathan Bentovish

Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

*Corresponding author

Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich), Zefat Academic Colloge, Zefat, Israel

Received: 25 Dec 2023

Accepted: 30 Dec 2023

Published: 03 Jan 2024

Copyright

© 2024 Jehonathan Bentovish

OPEN ACCESS

Note: Dr. Bentovish has been affiliated Ariel University & Zefat Academic Center, but is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in validating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics; Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentovish@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-first Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a Paradigmatic-Shift from the Old "Material-Causal-Random" MCR Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) following a fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" appearing in the Old Paradigm (e.g., signified by an apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and a principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe); Based upon the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions" (as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's Relativistic and Quantum Predictions), "G-D's Physics" is accepted as the New Twenty-First Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm! "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm stemming from the discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP) "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive "Universal Frame/s" (UF's) at an incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ": principally negates the Old MCR basic assumption wherein it is the direct "material-causal" physical interactions between a finite set of Relativistic or Quantum factors that can explain the universe's origination and development. Instead, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm recognizes this singular UCP as the sole "reality" underlying- and developing- the entire physical universe, according to a "Pre-planned" plan of steering the universe from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards fulfilling the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (and live accordingly!) Indeed, this New (and profound) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm recognizes the key central role of Humanity's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF, and associated Earth's localization) in bringing about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) associated with the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) two days' CHCF, and consequently also define Earth's CHCF as the "Functional Epicenter" of the universe! Hence, in stark contrast to the Old MCR Paradigm of GRT & QM, the New Twenty-First Century's "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm points at the UCP's "Pre-planned" universe leading from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity (which is beginning with the current acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm)!

Introduction

A "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal-Arbitrary" (MCA) Paradigm

We stand at a truly "historic turning point" in the history of Physics (and Science) more generally – following the appearance of a clear "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal-Arbitrary" (MCA) Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), and the discovery (and empirical validation) of a New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm shown capable of resolving this "Paradigmatic-Crisis", and offering an alternative satisfactory conception of the origination- development- and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe! This is because in a "deep philosophical" sense, this Old "Material-Causal-Arbitrary" (MCA) Paradigm – not only underlies Twentieth century's GRT & QM, but more fundamentally represent the basic "Cartesian-Materialistic-Arbitrary" conception of science, e.g., from its

very conception by Descartes through "Galilean/Copernican" Cosmology, through Darwinian Evolutionary Theory and Newtonian Classical Mechanics – and up till Einstein's GRT & QM! Fundamentally to all of these MCA's scientific models is the basic assumption wherein the universe can be explained strictly by "material-causal (arbitrary)" physical interaction/s between a finite set of physical or material entities, forces etc.?!

Hence, Einstein's GRT assumes that the universe was "created" (or "caused") by an initial ("random") "Big-Bang" nuclear event, e.g., which "created" all of the suns, galaxies, planets, mass and energy etc. in the universe! Likewise, GRT postulates that the development of the universe is "caused" by the direct "material-causal" physical interaction/s between certain "massive objects" and their "curvature of Space-Time" – which in turn "causes" (or determines) the "travelling pathways" of those "massive-objects" and other "less-massive" objects! In much the same manner, QM explains all of the "behavior" of subatomic particles based on the direct "material-causal

random" interaction/s between a given subatomic "probe" particle and a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function" which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of this "target's probability wave-function" into a singular (complimentary) "space-energy" or "mass-time" target's measured value! But, fundamental to Newton's preceding Classical Mechanics was also this "material-causal" (and "random") assumption: this is because Newton's Classical Mechanics' basic Laws of Motion all assume that every physical behavior of any given object (in the universe) can be described simply based on that given object's direct interaction/s with other objects or forces!? Likewise, the (preceding) basic "Galilean" and "Copernican" calculations of the travelling pathways of the different stellar components of our Solar System were also based on such "material-causal" (and "arbitrary") physical interactions between these objects, i.e., such as for instance the assumption that Earth revolves around the Sun due to the Sun's gravitational force exerted upon Earth's orbit!? In much the same manner, "Darwin's Natural Selection Process" (DNSP) also assumes that the evolution of the different biological species (on Earth) is "caused" by direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between certain "Genetically-Randomly-Mutated" (GRM) organisms and a given set of Environmental Factors" (EFs), which "causes" these "GRM" organisms to be "more compatible" to this (specific) "EFs", than other "Non-GRM" organisms – and hence "cause" the "survival" (and development) of only these GRM organisms, but not of the other Non-GRM organisms!

However, as noted (above and previously), this basic "Material-Causal-Random" Old Paradigm underlying GRT & QM (e.g., and in a "deep-philosophical" sense also all of the preceding Newtonian, Copernican, Galilean and all other Scientific Models such as DNSP etc.) has reached a state of a fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" – which necessitates Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics to seek an alternative satisfactory "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) which could resolve this basic "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of this Old "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) Paradigm, and offer a "broader" theoretical basis for our understanding of the "origin"- "development"- and "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe! This basic "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) Paradigm is characterized by the existence of a basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between the two basic "pillars" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm: "General Relativity Theory" (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and its principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the universe, e.g., assumed to be accounted for by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" concepts, but which failed to be detected empirically even after two full decades of intensive experimental efforts to do so!?

The basic fundamental Paradigmatic Shift brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm is anchored in its basic recognition of the fact that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame (e.g., since the singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, since according to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), there cannot exist any direct or indirect "material-causal" effect, "phenomenon" or interactions/s between any given UF's frame/s and any subsequent UF's frame/s! Therefore, according to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Principle" theoretical postulates, the physical universe of the universe does not exist as a "constant", "continuous" and "uniform" reality, but is rather seen as a "transient-phenomenal" reality which only exists "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, and is solely computed by the UCP (including the four basic physical features of "space", "energy" mass" and "time" for all exhaustive multifarious spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s), but "dissolves" back into the singularity of this higher-ordered UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, hence termed as "computationally-variant"!?

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) [1-47]! This "Paradigmatic-Shift" inevitably followed the appearance of a fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm signified by a basic "theoretical-inconsistency" between its (above-mentioned) constituting Models (e.g., GRT & QM), as well as its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, but could not be detected experimentally (despite over twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so)!? Instead, the New "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) has been shown capable of resolving this (apparent) "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM based on its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – in the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ (!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF's frames comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"!

According to [50] well-accepted analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions"[50], in order for science to accept such a "Paradigmatic-Shift" (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

a) The appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a "theoretical-inconsistency" between the "pillars" of the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!

b) The ability of the New ("G-D's Physics") Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP's) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) "particle/objects"; "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" (MST) "wave-phenomena"; and "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" "Universal Frame/s" computations! In this manner, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) as opposed to QM's "Quantum Entanglement" phenomena's implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic "entangled particle's" ("complimentary pairs" value may "instantaneously" affect the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to "G-D's Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more "constrictive" UCP's MST and SST computations, the apparent "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon merely represents the UCP's computation of "equivalent SST particle points" along the MST's (subatomic) "wave" computation, which is embedded within the broader EST UCP's computation! Alongside "G-D's Physics" new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" is based on the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" i.e., "Framework" and "Consistency" four possible combinations: "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), and "Object" – "con-

sistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") possible combinations! Hence, "G-D's Physics" new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict SLB's principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contradicted by Quantum Entanglement's "instantaneous" effect of the measurement of one entangled particle's complimentary pairs' measurement upon the other entangled particle's complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of "G-D's Physics" (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP's computation of "equivalent MST wave" "particle-points", coupled with its two "Computational Dimensions" complimentary exhaustive UCP's computation of "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time"), which can account for the apparent "entanglement" of two such "equivalent SST particle points" along the "MST wave" (simultaneous) computation of the UCP's "complimentary-exhaustive" "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") "complimentary pairs"!

Likewise, the New "G-D's Physics" theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe's empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of "G-D's Physics" is based on its (novel) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" (New Year) two days' special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an "UNCIARE" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique "Critical Prediction" which can differentiate the prediction of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM: according to Kuhn's50 analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm to the New ("G-D's Physics") Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate the predictions of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm from the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's and QM's predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm is verified as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions – then (according to Kuhn's50 well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we've been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to

this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i...n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i...n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [54-56].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

[54-56], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i...n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i...n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i...n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-

body force"[49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity[48], a new boson[52], and the quasi-free hypothesis

π^+ and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion[58-61]! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

The key "metamorphosis" brought about by the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm is quite profound: it alters our basic understanding of the physical universe – not as being "caused" or "governed" by any specific "material-causal" physical interactions, e.g., at either the Relativistic or Quantum levels: The universe could not have been "created" or "caused" by any (initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event, because there could not have existed any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels found within the "first", "second"... "nth" "Universal Frame/"s – since they are all being computed simultaneously by the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (or Universal Consciousness Reality", UCR)!! Neither could there exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (two or more) separate UF's frames, simply because all of the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP/UCR "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!?! Nor could the "development" or "evolution" of the universe (e.g., once again, at the macroscopic relativistic level or microscopic quantum level) can be explained through any direct or indirect physical interactions between any (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" and any postulated "galactic elements, or indeed, between any subatomic "probe" and "target" elements (which are assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of the target's assumed "probability wave function)!! This is (once again) due to the UCP's/UCR's simultaneous computation of all of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels' (four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") – for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of all of those universe's exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)!!

In fact, the profound change brought about by "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics) is associated with its discovery of two (far-reaching) theoretical postulates of the "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR): According to the "Computational Invariance Principle" since only this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) may be regarded as "computationally-invariant", e.g., as existing "uniformly", "continuously" and "constantly" – both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s and also exists without the presence of the physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; whereas the whole physical universe (and all of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is seen (for the first time in Physics) as representing only a "computationally-variant" phenomenon – i.e., existing only "transiently" and "phenomenally" "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely being computed by the UCP), but ceasing to exist and "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" every two consecutive UF's frame/s!?! Therefore, only this singular higher-ordered "UCP" may be regarded as "computationally-invariant", e.g., existing "constantly", "continuously" and "uniformly" both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (and as solely computing all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features comprising the entire physical universe depicted by each such consecutive UF's frame/s), and also solely existing "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence) of any physical universe; whereas the entire physical universe is seen as representing only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCP!?! Consequently, the "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulate goes further to highlight the fact that there truly exists only one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" which is this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) "computationally-invariant" reality – that exists both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s, (e.g., manifesting as the entire physical universe), and also exists solely without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive

This profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" – i.e., from a purely "Material-Causal" Paradigm assuming that the universe is "caused", "governed" and "developed" by mere (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions (e.g., such as the assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which is supposed to have "created" the suns, galaxies, planets, energy and mass in the universe, or the "material-causal" assumption wherein the continuous development of the physical universe is "caused" by the direct interaction/s between certain "massive objects" and "Space-Time" which "curves Space-Time", and conversely this "curved Space-Time" "causes" or "determines" the travelling-pathways of those "massive objects" and other "less-massive objects" etc.); To "G-D's Physics" more extensive understanding of the physical universe as representing a mere ("computationally-variant") "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) completely alters our basic understanding and appreciation of the true "origin", "nature" and higher underlying singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – i.e., which continuously "computes", "dissolves", "re-computes" and "develops" every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe towards an "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of the universe and of Humanity! This is because "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single or multiple UF's frame/s – due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any such UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such (exhaustive) spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) two "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulates, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm completely alters our basic understanding of the "true nature", "origin", "development" and even "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe! This is because not only do we understand that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (existing either in the "same" or "different") UF's frame/s; but more profoundly, we realize that there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests as the entire physical universe ("during" each consecutive UF's frame/s), and solely remains "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

So, we realize that the physical universe does not represent any "solid", "independent" "continuous" reality, but rather exists only as a manifestation of the true singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – which (solely) embodies it and also transcends it! Indeed, the (abovementioned) "A-Causal Computation" characterization of "G-D's Physics" new Scientific Paradigm, which (principally) negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels within the entire physical universe – i.e., existing within any single UF or across any two (different) UF's frame/s; teaches us that the sole "driving force" behind the "origination"- "sustenance"- "development"- and even "Ultimate Goal" of the "formation" and "existence" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is entirely dependent and contingent upon the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" that constitutes its sole "reality", and which exists "independently" (and "separately") from its "transient-phenomenal" manifestation as the physical universe! Indeed, "G-D's Physics" new realization wherein this singular higher-ordered UCR existence "transcends" it's only "transient-phenomenal" manifestation as the physical universe (e.g., "during" each consecutive UF's frame – as solely being computed by this singular higher-ordered UCR), alongside "G-D's Physics" discovery of this UCR's "Ten Hierarchical Computation-

al Dimensions" (THCD's) and associated "THCD's – Universal Computational Formula" (see below Figure and Diagram) reveal to us the real underlying "pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of this UCR to "steer" the entire physical universe – e.g., from its initial "inanimate" matter state through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of the universe (and Humanity), in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this singular higher-ordered UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which will also affect and characterize Humanity's understanding and behavior)!

A "Pre-Planned Geulah Driven Universe"!

We thus reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the universe could not have been "created" or ("caused") by any initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its development be explained by any (purely hypothetical and "undetectable") "dark-matter" or "dark-energy"?! but is rather being continuously computed- "dissolved"- "re-computed" and "developed"- by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)!" thereby producing an incredible rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's), which comprise the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal time-point"! Moreover, we realize that not only there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, but truly all of these exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., including their four associated physical features of "space",

"energy", "mass" and "time") – do not exist "independently" or "continuously", but rather only represent a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (e.g., which exists "constantly", "uniformly" and "continuously" both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists solely without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s)!

Hence, we realize that we cannot (any longer) view the universe's existence as governed by mere "material-causal" physical interaction/s, because such "material-causal" (e.g., direct or indirect) physical interactions cannot "exist" – either between two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels found within the "same" or "different" UF's (due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels of each consecutive UF's frame/s), or "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s, in which the whole universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP! We therefore must alter our basic understanding of the "origin"- true "nature", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe – as a mere "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality"! The physical universe exists – not as "independent", "solid", "continuous" reality, but is rather totally dependent upon- and in fact is only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of- the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which solely exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (exhaustive spatial pixels) and continues to exist without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two (such) consecutive UF's frame/s (in which all of those exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCR!) So, we begin realizing that the entire physical universe – truly only represents a continuous process of "manifestation" and "development" by this singular UCR, which constitutes the only "computational-invariant" "continuous", "uniform" and "constant" reality underlying- and (indeed) "transcending" the entire physical universe!

The next advancement in our understanding of the manner in which this singular UCR reality "originates", "sustains" ("dissolves") and "develops"

each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the universe as a whole) is related to the discovery of the UCR's (or UCP's) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" and associated "THCD's-Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF)!

Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions

The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's)

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah " State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!?! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah ' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah

Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic , "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/ חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and

awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/"נְבוֹרָה"):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" in order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Tiferet"/"תִּפְעָרֶת"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place

every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תִּפְעָרֶת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("Netzach"/"נֵצַח"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נֵצַח/Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"("תְּשׁוּבָה")/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva" / "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נֵצַח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Ob-

ject Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yesod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula" (THD-UCF):

mula"/"יסוד"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yesod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown"))"; This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ (sec) for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

The Centrality of “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) in “G-D’s Physics” New Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm and the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm is the “Centrality of Human Consciousness” – i.e., in “space” and “time”, and its intimate connection with the “Universal Consciousness Reality’s” (UCR’s) “Geulah Driven Universe” (GDU)! This is because according to “G-D’s Physics” New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) plays a major role in the “Universe’s Increase its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE)! As we’ve already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE’s acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and “G-D’s Physics” principle computational negation of its associated Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s SRCS Computational Structure!) – which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept can only account for a “constant-rate” expansion rate of the universe; the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., “UNCIARE” due to the “Collective Human Consciousness Focus”, which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah’s (two days’ special) time-interval!

Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on this CHCF that the universe’s rate of expansion” increases over time”, e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) “Universe’s Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UCAGUARE)!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days’ Jewish Rosh Hashanah – during September 16th& 17th 2023, in which it is predicted that the universe’s rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year, relative to the universe’s measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Sep. 16-17th! Moreover, previously it’s been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness – not just in “time” but also in “space”! This relates to the otherwise “unexplained” empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical measurement of the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion – i.e., related to “space”, wherein it is only relative to planet Earth’s position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! If (for instance) it is found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE – do not yield the same “symmetrical increase” in the universe’s UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) – in “space”, as well as in “time”!

“G-D’s Physics” Novel CHCF’s Center of the Universe Hypothesis!

We therefore reach an “astounding” new Hypothesis of “G-D’s Physics”, i.e., hypothesizing that at the center of the universe’s existence, dynamics and development – stand our planet Earth due to this CHCF, including the rotation of our sun (around it) and the accelerated expansion of other galactic elements “emanating” from planet Earth’s CHCF! This is because once we realize that the evolution of the physical universe cannot be explained merely due to an any initially assumed “Big-Bang” nuclear event- e.g., based on the empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm (above); and that (in fact), the basic SRCS Computational Structure of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm was shown to be negated by “G-D’s Physics” (novel) “Computational Duality Principle” (CDP) – i.e., as inevitably leading to both “log-

ical-inconsistency” and (ensuing) “computational indeterminacy” that are both negated by the CDP’s insistence upon the (proven) capacity of this apparently SRCS Computational System to determine the accelerated expansion of the universe – which (according to the CDP) points at the singularity of this singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s)! And most significantly, empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” (above) unique “Critical Prediction” regarding the “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) – as more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s assumed “constant rate” of the universe’s expansion rate! Therefore, we must negate (and reject) the Old “Material-Causal” GRT’s Paradigm’s assumption wherein the entire physical universe has been created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear even, and that its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (which has been negated based on the three abovementioned considerations)!?

The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that (solely) exists both “during” its computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel’s four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP’s connection with the CHCF – which brings about the UCP’s initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated by the “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion”, CAGUARE) is brought about by the UCP’s consecutive computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s – and specifically by the CHCF’s UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual “Jewish Rosh-Hashanah” two days’ time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Sep. 16-17th 2023 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe’s expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe’s expansion prior to the 16-17th – which I’ve called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe “dissolves” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF’s frame/s; and therefore that the only “force” that creates- “dissolves”- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF – which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe’s expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year).

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein taking together these two empirically validated facts:

a) Empirical Validation of “G-D’s Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, which according to G-D’s Physics is associated with the CHCF (e.g., specifically during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashanah” special two days’ time interval, as noted above: a call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test this UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 & onwards!) In other words, this UNCIARE (JRH) empir-

ically confirmed phenomenon points at the centrality of CHFC “in time”, i.e., specifically during the JRH (e.g., to be directly confirmed through the above call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test during the upcoming JRH!)

b) Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! The empirically observed “unexplained” “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (CAGUARE) (indicates that the rate of the universe's expansion has increased (significantly) from its early “Background Radiation” stage to the current (increased) rate in the universe's expansion!)? This phenomenon is associated with Planet Earth's “Epicenter” of the universe – in “space” (e.g., based on the fact that the accelerated rate of our regions of the universe is proportional to the distance from “Earth”!)

Taken together, these empirically validated (major otherwise “unexplained”) phenomena point at the centrality of Earth's “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” – in “space” and “time”: as the (functional) center of the universe! It also reinforces the singularity of the higher ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” as the sole source “originating” the entire physical universe (at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ (sec}^2\text{)}$!)

Indeed, over and beyond the abovementioned empirical validations of “G-D's Physics” two unique “Critical Predictions”, e.g., associated with the “UNCIARE” and “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings, the two above empirical findings, i.e., regarding: a) Empirical Validation of “G-D's Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which according to G-D's Physics is associated with the CHCF; b) Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! clearly point at the Earth's CHCF's associated “Epicenter of the Universe” – i.e., both in “time” & “space”! Once again, if we wish to further validate in an even more direct manner the centrality of “Earth's Epicenter of the Universe” (EEU) related to its CHCF (EEU-CHCF), then Astronomers are invited to test two additional unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm:

1) UNCIARE-JRH: as noted (above), an even more direct empirical validation of “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” New Scientific Paradigm, relates to a further testing of its additional “Critical Prediction” regarding the UNCIARE at the (upcoming) JRH (Sep. 16-17th 2023) in which it is predicted that the rate of the universe's expansion will increase during these two days (and continue constantly throughout the next Jewish Year, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion rate prior to Sep. 16-17th)!

2) EEU Validation: “Non-Earth's Non-Epicenter Measurements” (NENEM)! An additional (even more direct) testing of the Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion would be an empirical validation of a measurement of the universe's “non-harmonious”, i.e., “non-equivalent” accelerated expansion rate – of the farthest regions of the universe, when measured at a location “distant” from Earth (e.g., such as for instance from “Mars” or other “distant” Non-Earth location)! This is because, if indeed, any such measurement of the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (of a greater rate of expansion proportional to the distance from Earth's measurement) would be found to be “un-equivalent” (in all directions – for all furthest regions of the universe), as opposed to the accelerated (“equivalent” or “harmonious”) rate of the universe's expansion as measured from “Earth's Universe's Epi-center” (EEU), then this would indicate that indeed Earth's (CHCF) Epicenter is in fact that the (functional) center of the entire physical universe!

In order to be able to accept this new (profound) metamorphosis of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which assume that the universe was created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang”

nuclear event (and is expanding due to a purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept which could not be verified experimentally and which is negated by the New empirically validated “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm, it is necessary to “retrace” the emergence of the basic “Paradigmatic-Crisis”, e.g., signifying this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm: indicated by the fundamental “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and its principle inability to explain the empirically observed accelerated rate of the universe's expansion – assumed to be “caused” by the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be verified experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so over the past two full decades?!). As we've seen, such a (fundamental) “Paradigmatic-Crisis” characterizes (according to Thomas Kuhn's 1962 famous analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”) the need for an ensuing “Paradigmatic-Shift” from this Old “Material-Causal” New “G-D's Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! Indeed, the acceptance of the New “A-Causal Computation” “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm is dependent upon the fulfillment of few (stringent) criteria including: a) Capacity of the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm to resolve the (apparent) GRT-QM “theoretical inconsistency” (which has been shown previously stemming from the discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^2$! thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!) b) Offering an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – based on the UNCIARE's associated CHCF (outlined above); c) Identification- and empirical validation- of at least one unique “Critical Prediction/s” of “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions! (Indeed, the abovementioned empirical validations of two such unique “Critical Predictions” related to UNCIARE and the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings indicate that “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm is more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's GRT and QM's corresponding predictions!)

Hence, based upon the fulfillment of these (stringent) necessary conditions for the acceptance of “G-D's Physics” (CUFT) – points at “G-D's Physics” as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! It is important to note that this New “G-D's Physics” was shown to resolve the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM – and in fact unify between them based on its discovery of the (novel) “Universal Computational Formula”, which was also shown to unify (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”), as well as between the Four Forces! Nevertheless, the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm was characterized as an “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, stemming from its discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF's frames (back into the singularity of the UCP)! According to this New “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s! This profound new discovery made by the New “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm principally negates some of the most basic assumptions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, including: GRT's “Big-Bang Model” and the existence of any purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept (as the assumed “caused” for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, as explained above).

Instead, “G-D's Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm points at the fact that the whole origination-

sustenance- "dissolution"- and development of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety) has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP to evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which is also characterized by Humanity's (and Science's) "embracing" of this singular UCP's/UCR's intrinsic properties of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"! Thus, the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm explains the whole origination- sustenance- ("dissolution"-) and development- of the entire physical universe: not as created by an initial "random" "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and the whole development of the universe – as leading to an ("inevitable") "dissipation" (e.g., based on the Second Law of Thermodynamics), which was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its CDP; but rather as being "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" (e.g., Morally, Spiritually and even Physically)! In that sense, the (above) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions"

A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the

whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

We therefore begin realizing that the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe is driven by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which has "preplanned" the whole development of the entire physical universe in order to reach that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! We realize that since the UCP is the sole "computationally-invariant" Principle (or "reality") that can "produce"- "sustain"- "dissolve"- or "evolve" any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as "originate"- "sustain" and "evolve" the entirety of the physical universe! And moreover, since that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is continuously "originating"- "evolving"- ("dissolving"-) and "developing" the entire physical universe – is "motivated" by this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's intrinsic "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and geared towards fulfilling the Universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" State of the Universe (and of Humanity)! Therefore, we are "astonished" to find out that at every "trillionth-of-trillionth etc." of a second (e.g., " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 sec!) this UCP computes and evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – including all human-beings, animals, plants and even "inanimate matter" based upon the UCP's THCD's (and associated THCD's-UCF!) which is "steering" the universe (and Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and begin living in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

The important point to be noted (here) is that we begin noticing that the manner in which this UCP computes- sustains- ("dissolves"-) and evolves- every exhaustive spatial pixel (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) relies upon its THCD's extremely rapid computation, e.g., at the rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 sec! in which the "Human Collective Consciousness Focus" (as well as the Individual Human Consciousness Moral Choice/s) plays a key central role, alongside this singular higher-ordered UCP's "steering" of Humanity and the Universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! This is because, when we closely examine those THCD's we notice two very important elements:

a) The sixth Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of the Universe's Expansion (NCARUE) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) – determines the universe's increase in

the universe's accelerated rate of expansion, i.e., beginning at each JRH's two days' special time-interval! (This year the UNCIARE-JRH took place during Sep. 16th-17th, 2023, for which there was an urgent Call for Astronomers to validate the increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion beginning in these two days and subsequently, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to these two days' JRH time-interval! Data is still missing regarding this urgent call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to validate this year's Sep. 16-17th UNCIARE.) Nevertheless, one of the two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which have been empirically validated as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM is this UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction! As shown above, this "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) "Critical Prediction" was validated empirically based on the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE) which supports "G-D's Physics" annual increase at the JRH's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) two days' time-interval! Indeed, such a CAGUARE cannot be accounted for GRT's "constant-rate" expansion of the universe due to the (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" concepts – but precisely confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction"! This is because based on "G-D's Physics" CHCF postulate which takes place every consecutive JRH's (two days' time interval and remains constant throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year) it is expected that the universe's expansion rate will increase "over time", i.e., leading to the observed CAGUARE's UNCIARE-JRH phenomenon!

b) Earth's CHCF "Functional Center" of the Universe – In "Space" & "Time"!?

Indeed, the existence of "Hubbles Law" (HL), e.g., indicating that the rate of the universe's expansion – relative to "Earth's Functional Epicenter" increases as a function of the distance of any give galaxy from "Earth's Functional Epicenter" points at Earth functioning as the "Universe's Functional Epicenter"! Moreover, when we take into consideration the combination of HL's Earth's Functional Center together with the (abovementioned) CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH we must reach the inevitable conclusion wherein Earth's CHCF stands at the basis of Earth's Functional Center – i.e., both in "space" and "time"! In other words, the clear empirical evidence positioning Earth as the "Functional Center" of the universe, as evidenced by HL & associated CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH indicate that Earth's CHCF is responsible for Earth's UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., every consecutive Jewish Year), and when taken together with HL indicate that Earth's CHCF serves as the "Functional Center" of the entire physical universe both in "space" and "time"!?

c) The UCP's "Non-Continuous Computation of the Universe" (UCP-NC-CU)!

The next "step" in our new understanding of the fundamental "metamorphosis" that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm creates in our basic understanding of the true "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe is associated with "G-D's Physics" other unique "Critical Prediction" validation, e.g., associated with the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's computation of the entire physical universe (as well as of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is "non-continuous", i.e., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., therefore the whole physical universe has been redefined as representing only a "computationally-variant" manifestation of the singular "computationally-invariant" UCP which exists "constantly, continuously and uniformly" both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely existing without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!) Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (second) "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings' unique "Critical Pre-

dition" – differentially predicted this "Proton Radius Puzzle" key findings, wherein the relatively "more massive" Muon particle would be computed by the UCP as more "spatially-consistent" than the relatively "less-massive" electron particle (across a series of UF's frame/s)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the UCP's computation of any given particle's "mass" value is based on the UCP's "Object-consistent" computation of each given particle – i.e., with more massive particles being computed as more "spatially-consistent" (as outlined previously) This leads to the UCP's computation of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle as being more "spatially-consistent" than the less-massive electron particle, which then leads to the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings of the relatively "smaller, more accurate measurements" of the Hydrogen's Proton Radius – when encircled by the relatively "more massive" Muon particle, than when encircled by the "standard electron" particle! But, implied within this empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Proton-Radius Puzzle" "Critical Prediction" is the realization that the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe) – is "non-continuous", i.e., "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, as indicated above, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in either the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s, which also implies that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As shown above, "G-D's Physics" two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates indicated that the only manner in which the "computationally-variant" universe is "originated", ("dissolved"),sustained and "developed" – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec" is based upon the UCP's THCD's-UCF, which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards reaching the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah" State of the universe, in which both Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony"!

Since the UCP's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe relates to Humanity's attainment of such a "Perfected Geulah State", in which all human-beings realize their "oneness" with this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., including their realization of the UCP's basic fundamental "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle": which "teaches" every individual human-being to regard any other human-being as "integral inseparable parts" of this same singular higher-ordered UCP, therefore we see that the UCP's execution of every consecutive UF's exhaustive spatial pixels – strongly relates to its computation of each individual human-being's Moral Choice/s at every "minimal time-point", including the (previously delineated) possibility of "Teshuvah" (e.g., corresponding to the UCP's eighth "Teshuva" HCD, which allows every human-being to carry out a sincere "Teshuvah" remorse and conscious decision to not repeat any specific immoral action); which then alters and changes the UCP's computation of the subsequent (ninth) "UCP's Actual Computed Object", (i.e., in terms of "avoiding" and "altering" that individual human-being's next subsequent UF's frame/s presentation of an "equivalent negative situation" in which that individual human-being would have to experience the same "negative immoral situation" which he/she inflicted pain/suffering upon any other individual human-being – since that individual human-being has carried out a genuine "teshuvah" regarding his/her "immoral choice/s")! So, we can see that at the very center of the UCP's continuous creation- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe's development) stands the UCP's

consideration of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – at the JRH's two-days' time-interval, which brings about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCI-ARE), as well as the UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle which affects that UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in any subsequent UF's frame/s of the universe), and advances the whole of Humanity towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe!

Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Seven Days Origination" (USDO) Model

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Seven Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDO Model of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

a) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

b) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "materi-

al-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!")

c) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

d) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

e) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

f) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [CAGUARE]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th & 17th, 2023 (e.g., relative to prior to Sep 16th-17th, and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate CAGUARE (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above

and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above)!

g) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF that allowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

h) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec) based primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion! Hence, it's become clear that Science (and Humanity) have now reached a "critical turning point" in its development: instead of Science's "lifelong" basic "Material-Causal" assumption (e.g., including even "Newtonian Classical Mechanics") wherein it was assumed that everything in the universe can be explained as being "caused" by a certain "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any given (finite) number of material elements!? Such as GRT's basic assumption, wherein the origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, or the expansion of the universe is "caused" by the purely hypothetical "Dark Matter" or "Dark-Energy" concepts? Or such as QM's assumed determination of any given subatomic particle or wave entity based on the direct physical interaction/s of a given subatomic "probe" element with a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function", which "causes" this (assumed) "target's probability wave function" to "collapse" into a single "complimentary" "space-energy" or "mass-time" value?! The New empirically validated "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm completely negated such basic "Material-Causal" assumption – e.g., due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm advanced our new (higher) understanding wherein the only manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) continuously "originates", "sustains", ("dissolves") and "develops" the entire physical universe is based upon its "pre-planned" Blueprint Plan of "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and

human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the entire physical universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP as the sole reality behind the universe (e.g., and also transcending its existence); which will also include Humanity's recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's "peaceful", "meaningful" and "harmonious" ("goodwill") existence!

The "robustness" of any given Scientific Theory, i.e., and especially the discovery and empirical validation of a New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) in any given discipline – far exceeds its ability (merely) to satisfy the necessary (stringent) criteria to accept this NSP, as more "valid" (and "satisfactory") than the Old Paradigm! As mentioned earlier, according to Thomas Kuhn's (1962) famous (and well-accepted) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", the appearance of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) ensues the existence of basic fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the "Old Paradigm" – in our case this is the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, characterized by an apparent basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" which are supposed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which could not be detected or verified experimentally (despite two full decades of trying to do so?!)

"G-D's Physics" Account of the Origin- Sustenance- Development & Goal of the Universe!

The amazing characteristics of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is that in addition to its unique capacity – not only to unify (for the first time in Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") as well as between the Four Forces (e.g., strong- and weak- nuclear, electromagnetic and gravitational forces), as well as between GRT & QM (e.g., within a single "Universal Computational Formula!"); is that it also offers an exhaustive portrayal of the whole origination- sustenance- development- and even "Ultimate Goal" of the universe's existence and development! Indeed, based on "G-D's Physics" (novel) "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, e.g., which negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels which exist either in the "same"- or "different"- UF's frame/s, i.e., due to the "simultaneity" of this singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s; "G-D's Physics New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm's "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) unequivocally points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels of the entire physical universe (e.g., for every consecutive "Universal Frame" [UF] at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec!)

We therefore realize that in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) which assumed that everything in the universe can be explained as "caused" by (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between a finite set of physical elements: GRT assumes that the physical universe was "created" (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which created all of the suns, galaxies, energy etc. in the universe, and that the whole evolution of the entire physical universe may be explained merely based on Einstein's Equations' interactions between certain "massive objects" and "Space-Time", which "causes" the "curvature of Space-Time", which in turn determines (or "causes") the "travelling pathways" of those "massive" or other "less-massive" objects!? Similarly, GRT's Einstein's Equations assume that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion is "caused" by (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Mat-

ter" or "Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) who are assumed to "directly interact" with certain "galactic-elements", thereby "causing" the expansion of the universe?! Likewise, Quantum Mechanics assumes that the only manner in which we can know of any subatomic "target particle's" physical features – is by sending a corresponding "probe particle" that directly interacts with this "target's particle's" assumed "probability wave function", that "causes" the "collapse" of the subatomic "target's probability wave-function" into a singular (complimentary) "space-energy" or "mass-time" value?! But, since the New (empirically proven) "G-D's Physics' A-Causal" Scientific Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions (e.g., due to the singular higher-ordered UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's Frame/s; and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm was shown to strictly negate any of these Relativistic or Quantum "manifestations" of the Old "Material-Causal" basic assumption, e.g., regarding the Big-Bang Model, Einstein's Equations' assumed direct physical interaction between (certain) "massive objects" and "caused curvature of Space-Time", or its assumed DM/DE's "causing" of the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, or QM's assumed "collapse" of the "target's probability wave function"! Instead, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels of the entire physical universe (at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of Universal Frames (UF's) of the whole universe at ever "minimal time-point"! Indeed, the New "G-D's Physics" strict negation of the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm is perhaps most clear and evident through "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) "Computational Duality Principle" (as previously outlined)

The "Computational Invariance Principle" & "Universal Consciousness Reality"!

The next (profound) "leap" in our basic conceptual understanding of the "origination" and "true nature of the" entire physical – brought about by "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm is represented by two of its (novel) theoretical postulates, namely: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality"; according to the "Computational Invariance Principle", since only singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" is considered as "computationally-invariant", e.g., exists "constantly", "consistently" and "uniformly" – both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists solely (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; whereas the four basic physical features comprising the entire physical universe exist only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed by this singular higher-ordered UCP), but cease to exist and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s and are therefore considered merely as "computationally variant" – i.e., exist only "transiently" and "phenomenally" ("during" each consecutive UF's frame/s but not "in-between" them)?! Therefore, according to this (novel) "Computational Invariance Principle", the only "computationally-invariant" principle that exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exist (solely) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe) – is this singular higher-ordered "computationally-invariant" "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP)! Moreover, according to the associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulate, since only this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is considered as "computationally-invariant", e.g., exists "constantly", "continuously" and "consistently" (e.g., both "during" its computation of every consecutive

UF's frame/s, and also solely exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); whereas the entire physical universe (including its four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" which are being computed for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s by this singular higher-ordered UCP) is considered as only "computationally-variant", i.e., existing only "transiently" and "phenomenally", as solely – "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP!?) therefore according to this (novel) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), there truly exists only one singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists "constantly", "continuously" and "consistently" – both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, in which it "manifests" in the physical universe, and also solely exist (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

On the "Non-Continuous" Nature of the Physical Universe!

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire physical universe does not exist as a "solid-continuous" "objective reality", but rather only "transiently" and "phenomenally" – being continuously "computed", "dissolves", "re-computed" and "evolved" by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), i.e., of which the entire physical universe is merely a "transient-phenomenal manifestation"! This "striking" new realization, that the entire physical universe does not exist "continuously" or "constantly", but is rather being continuously "computed", "dissolved", "re-computed" and "evolved" simultaneously at each of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels by this singular higher-ordered UCR (e.g., at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) completely revises our basic (hitherto) understanding of the "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe! This is because, instead of the universe being "created" (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, which is assumed to have created all of the "mass" and "energy" ("space" and "time") in the universe – as we've already seen, according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, no such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s could exist between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, or indeed "in between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!?) due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP/UCR "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, at a more basic conceptual level, our fundamental appreciation of the whole entire physical universe (e.g., and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it!) is being "dramatically" altered, based on the discovery (and acceptance) of "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulates!

This is because instead of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption, wherein every phenomenon throughout the entire physical universe can be explained simply based on a series of (direct or indirect) "material-physical" interaction/s between a finite set of "physical elements", which is being strictly "challenged" and (in fact) "negated" by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's insistence that there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels throughout the entire physical universe (e.g., existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s!?) – due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and their complete "dissolution" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm leads us towards a completely new (profound) understanding of the "true nature", "continuous origination" (and even "Ultimate Goal" of the universe) as being underlie (and "transcended")

by this singular higher-ordered UCR!? Not only there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (found in the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s), but more fundamentally, the whole existence of the entire physical universe is "non-continuous"! This is because the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! This means that "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s the whole universe "dissolves" back into the UCP, so that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions – both "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the whole universe), or "across" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (due to the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe back into the singularity of the UCP!)

Indeed, the abovementioned empirical results point at this basic "non-continuity" of the existence of the physical universe – in terms of its "temporal" aspect of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE), as indicated by the "Cosmological Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE)! Another indirect indication of the universe's "non-continuous" nature, e.g., as being constantly (and continuously) "computed" "dissolved", "re-computed" and "evolved" by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) was given through the (abovementioned) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! This is because in contrast to the principle inability of Quantum Mechanics to account for the "smaller" and "more accurate" measurement of the Hydrogen's Proton (radius) – when surrounded (and later on "sunk-en into") more massive "Muon" particle, as opposed to the standard Hydrogen atom (surrounded by the equivalent negatively charged electron particle); "G-D's Physics" unique "Critical Prediction" is closely associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" novel computational definitions of the four basic physical features, e.g., as computed by the UCP's two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" ("frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent"), the computational definition of the "mass" value of any given particle is computed as the degree of the "Object's-consistency" (e.g., or "spatial-consistency") across a series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) that is computed by the UCP/UCR! This implies that a relatively "more massive" particle (such as the Muon) will be computed as more "spatially-consistent" than a relatively "less-massive" particle such as the electron, and therefore since this (more massive) Muon "sinks" into the nucleus of the Hydrogen it is also associated with the Proton's measured "smaller" and "more accurate" radius! The important point to note (in this context) is that the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique "Critical Predictions": the "UNCIARE" and "Proton Radius Puzzle" phenomena support- and point at the "non-continuity" of the physical universe, as being "computed"- "dissolved"-, "re-computed"- and "evolved"- by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" or UCR (so many "trillions" of times each second: $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$); and also at the centrality of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"- as the functional center of the entire physical universe, i.e., both in "time" and in "space"!

"G-D's Physics" New "Gimatria", "Dynamic-Moral Principle" & "Geulah Driven" Universe!

We now reach the "culmination" of our new understanding of the physical universe, which is based on the entire corpus of over 100 scientific (peer-reviewed) articles dedicated to the discovery, delineation and empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! We've already seen that the entire physical universe does not exist "continuously" or "independently" of its continuous "computation"- "dissolution"- "re-computation" and "development" by the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR); and in fact, that the entire

physical universe may be viewed (or regarded) merely as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which exists only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed by this singular UCR: simultaneously for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s), but "ceases" to exist, and "dissolves" back into the singularity or the UCP/UCR "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As also described in previous articles (Bentovish, see detailed References) the UCP's extremely rapid computation of the series of Universal Frames (and of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising it) is primarily based upon a few characteristics associated with the UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions and associated Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula (THCD's-UCF), including its delineation of the Gimatria's (alphabetic Hebrew numeric values associated with each letter comprising the Hebrew name of any given object or even person!) Generally speaking, we may describe the "extremely complex" and "infinitely intelligent" capacities of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (or UCR), there are "six layers" (or phases) of this singular UCP/UCR:

a) The UCP's Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's: "General Blueprint Universal Plan" (GCC, CMD, DEMP, GDD)

The Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's comprise the "General Blueprint Plan" for the UCP outlines the continuous "origination"- "sustenance" and "development" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe, e.g., in which the singularity of the UCP will be recognized by Humanity (and Science) alongside its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality". "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's existence and behavior! It therefore "contains" the key "Consistency Computational Principles" guiding the UCP's execution of the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' operation, as well as all other ensuing computations carried out by the next five successive levels of the UCP (delineated below); Generally speaking, it contains these "Computational Principles":

1) Consciousness-Moral Development (CMD)

Relates to the UCP's "General Guiding Principle" of "steering" the whole universe from its initial "inanimate" matter state through successive "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – leading towards Humanity's Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state! (It should be mentioned that due to "G-D's Physics' Collective Human Consciousness Focus theoretical postulate and empirical validation of its unique UNCIARE "Critical Prediction" based on the abovementioned Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (CAGUARE), therefore this CMD Guiding Principle is also associated with "G-D's Physics" "Six Days' Creation Model", SDCM, as outlined above)

2) The "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP)

Another key "General Guiding Principle" is one of the THCD's called" the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP) which also characterizes one of the "sublime characteristics" of the UCP/UCR associated with its Moral nature! According to this DEMP, the UCP contains a "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" which comprises all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being based on his/her "Moral Choice/s" (at every point in time)! According to this UCP's DEMP ("Guiding Principle") whenever any individual human-being makes (for instance) any "immoral choice" ("G-d forbid") and inflicts "pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being, then this "triggers" the UCP's DEMP's "balancing moral computation" which computes an equivalent "negative situation" in which that individual human-being that "inflicted pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being would have to experience ("G-d forbid") an "equivalently negative situation" – that would

most likely) lead him/her to make "Teshuvah", (e.g., a Jewish term denoting a sincere sense of remorse and associated conscious decision not to repeat any such "immoral choice/s"! Indeed, as outlined above (and previously), to the extent that any such individual human-being makes such a sincere "Teshuvah" (also represented by the eighth HCD of "Teshuva" ("הוה"), then this will "prevent" and (indeed) "omit" the UCP's ("need" to present) any subsequent "equivalent negative situation" UF's frame/s (for that individual human-being), because the whole "purpose" of the UCP's execution of the DEMP is to "balance", correct" and "steer" each individual human-being towards a "morally-balanced" state of Humanity in which the whole of Humanity views and regards each other as "inseparable parts" of the same singular higher-ordered Moral "Universal Consciousness Reality"! (As noted previously, the same UCP's DEMP also "renumerates" each individual human-being by presenting an "equivalent-positive" situation for any "good moral choice/s" made by any individual human-being to assist another individual human-being as well!)

3) Geulah Directed Development (GDD)!

Perhaps the most important (key) "Guiding Principle" is the UCP's "Geulah-Directed Development" (GDD) of the whole physical universe – whose whole "pre-planning" by the singular higher-ordered UCP has been geared and directed to attain this "Ultimate-Geulah Goal Perfected State" of the universe! It therefore "overarches" and "leads" the other (abovementioned) two UCP's "Guiding Principles" – all aimed at fulfilling this UCP's (singular higher-ordered) "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal"! Therefore, we can see that this "germinal" "Geulah Perfected Goal" of the UCP (e.g., including its three abovementioned ensuing Consistency Computation elements of: CMD, DEMP & GDD)

b) The Seven Secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) "Geulah-Directed Universe"!

Based upon the TKI-HCCD's (three initial HCD's) "General Blueprint Plan" for the whole origination, sustenance and development of the universe then leads to the "secondary layer" of the "Seven Secondary HCD's" which are utilized by the UCP as its means for "executing" and "directing" the continuous development of the universe (e.g., and of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) – which are aimed at "steering" the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity & Science! As we can clearly see in the Diagram (and as outlined and delineated in previous articles), the Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's provide us with a detailed "Geulah Directed Blueprint Plan for "steering" the universe towards this "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" – based on the (first HCD of the UCP's) "Wisdom/Free Will" "desire" to create the world (and specifically our planet Earth – filled with the various forms of inanimate matter, and animate: plants, animals, all leading to the creation of human-beings endowed with a unique conscious "Moral-Choice"!); subsequently, the second HCD of "Computation" also contains the UCP's "Consistency" CMD "germinal" conception (e.g., comprising the conception of the universe's whole entire development from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings and leading up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected" State! The next seven HCD's actually execute (and fulfill) the UCP's DEMP & GDD "Guiding Principles" (as previously delineated)! Succinctly stated, the fourth HCD of "Goodwill/DEMP" represents the UCP's DEMP's enables each individual human-being (e.g., as well as the whole of Humanity) to "balance" and in fact "enhance" his/her "Moral Stance", i.e., assisting Humanity (and each individual human-being comprising it) to realize our "inseparability" from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, and therefore "stop" and (principally) "negate" any "negative-immoral" action and in fact enhance (and "encourage") all "moral-good behavior" towards our fellow human-beings! The fourth HCD of "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" represents the actual execution of the UCP's "bank" of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" (e.g., contained within the whole corpus of the "pre-planned course" of the universe's "Complete Journey" from its initial "inanimate" matter through

"animate": plants, animals and human-beings – and all of the "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being necessary in order to bring Humanity towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe! The sixth HCD of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah": CHCF-JRH) represents the UCP's allocation of a single (whole) Jewish Year (segment) from the (previous "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" spanning the whole "preplanned corpus" of the entire universe's development) containing all of the necessary "events" and "situations" found within a single "Jewish Year" that are "pre-planned" to "execute" and "balance" the DEMP in order to "uplift" Humanity "ever-closer" to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" (e.g., during this New Jewish Year)! The seventh HCD of the "UCP's Computed Potential Object" relates (according to "G-D's Physics" previously delineated novel computational definitions of any given "Object's") two associated physical features of "mass" (i.e., "Object-consistent") and "time" (i.e., "Object-inconsistent")! This seventh UCP's HCD computation takes into account all previous UCP's HCD's cumulating any given "Object's" (e.g., any individual human-being's according to his/her "moral-choice/s", or any other "animate" or "animate" "Object's" associated moral value/s and ensuing DEMP's based computed "Object" ("mass" and "time" values)! Subsequently, the UCP's eighth HCD of "Teshuvah" (as outlined above) allows for the possibility of any individual human-being's making a sincere "teshuva" (e.g., as explained above and previously) – which then "alters" (and even "prevents") the UCP's presentation of any potentially "negative situation/s" for any given individual human-being based on such a (sincere) "teshuva" (by that individual human-being)! The ninth HCD of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object Four Physical Features" represents the UCP's culmination of the actual computation for the next (subsequent) UF's frame's computation of the four basic physical features (e.g., of "mass", "energy", "space" and "energy") – based on all of the previous eight HCD's! Note that this ninth UCP's "Actual Computed Object" – even though it contains also the two (additional) "Frame" related physical features, e.g., "Frame-consistent" ("space") and "Frame-inconsistent" ("energy") – it still "lacks" the actual ability to "materialize" any given exhaustive spatial pixel or any object (based upon these extremely complex and intelligent computations)!? According to "G-D's Physics THCD's detailed analysis, this requires the "infinite intelligence and power" of the UCP- which Itself "executes" and "carries out" this "materialization" of all exhaustive spatial pixels and objects in the universe (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s) in the Tenth HCD's "UCP's 'Infinite' Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization!" Indeed, as we will see in the accumulation of all the five detailed "layers" (or phases) of the UCP's singular (extremely complex) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (and objects) in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) far exceeds even our most "wild imagination" regarding the "infinite": "complexity", "intelligence" and "power" required in order to accumulate and integrate these "disparate" ("infinitely complex") five (integrated) lawyer of the UCP's (simultaneous) computation for each exhaustive spatial pixel/s in the universe!

It is important to note that "encapsulated" within the Seven Secondary HCD's are also found the Geulah Directed Development (GDD) – found within the "Good-Will" HCD; the entire "Conscious-Moral Development" (CMD) – found within the "Multi-Spatial-Temporal-Reservoir" (MSTR) containing the UCP's "reservoir" of all the UF's of the entire universe's "pre-planned history", i.e., corpus of all "past", "present" and "future" UF's frame/s, e.g., including its development from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe!)

c) Gimatria Based UCP's Computation of All Exhaustive Spatial Pixels' Objects!

Next, we have to add the UCP's (successive) computation of every exhaustive spatial object in the universe – in terms of the UCP's computation of its "physical characteristics" based on its Hebrew name's "Gimatria":

i.e., alphabetic-numeric value/s comprised of each of its "five" (or less or more) letters which correspond to the (Seven Secondary HCD's) initial five HCD's: Good-Will (חסד), MSTR (גבורה), UNCIARE-JRH (תפארת), UCP's Potential Computed Object (נצח), Teshuva (הוד). According to "G-D's Physics" novel conception of the manner in which the UCP "originates" all exhaustive objects in the universe (previously delineated) the UCP extremely rapid computation of the series of UF's (comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point") at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec!" the UCP "allocates" "five zero's out of the 50 zero's (e.g., power of minus 50!) – the first 5 zeroes are allocated to the UCP's computation of the given object's first (Seven Secondary HCD's) of "Good-Will" which is associated that object's first letter (e.g., as it is computed relative to the other four remaining letters in that five-letter object's name; if there are less- or more- than those five "template" Gimatria Based UCP's computation, then there is a "compensation" or "addition" by the missing letters that are added to the "missing" letters or "last fifth letter"!)

Thus, for instance the Hebrew word for a human-being is "אדם" which only contains three letters: the Gimatria alphabetic value of the first letter "א" is "1" – which is assigned to the first (Secondary Seven) HCD of "Good-Will" ("חסד") which receives the highest value in terms of the "core characterization" of the "spiritual facet" underlying this object's subsequent Four Physical Features! If we were to give a metaphoric image to the manner in which these "Gimatria-based" alphabetic numeric values are associated with groups of "five zero's" – for each of these five initial (Seven Secondary HCD's): Good-Will (חסד), MSTR (גבורה), UNCIARE-JRH (תפארת), UCP's Potential Computed Object (נצח), Teshuva (הוד) are subsequently translated into the Four Physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"); we could use the metaphor of "large babushka" the famous "Russian doll" that comprises up to 5 or 7 smaller (same image but smaller dolls) contained within this "large babushka" doll! If we imagine a scenario in which this whole "large babushka doll" is created from "within- outwardly"; i.e., beginning with the innermost smallest babushka doll, and then covering an enlarging and encapsulating this "smallest babushka doll" within ever growing "babushka-dolls"! we can notice a surprising "finding" – i.e., that even though the "smallest babushka doll" cannot be seen when it is encapsulated by all of the "larger babushka dolls", when we focus on the "shape" of the "large babushka doll" – we suddenly realize that it is (in fact) the initial "shape" (and "characteristics") of the "small babushka doll" that actually "molded" (and in fact "determined") the "shape" (and characteristics) of the "large babushka doll"! This is because (we realize) that each successive "larger babushka doll" has to "conform" and "replicate" (while "enlarging") the "original small babushka doll's shape"! This metaphor implies that there is a greater strength to the initial letters of any object's name – relative to its subsequent letters, which "mold" the basic "characteristics" of the "spiritual facets" of this object, e.g., in consideration: both of the special ("spiritual") elements of each Hebrew letter and its associated semantic meaning/s, its Gimatria numeric value and its association with one of the five initial (Seven Secondary HCD's, listed above – with the former HCD's bearing a "greater weight" in molding the "spiritual characteristics" of the given object's later physical features)! Thus, for instance, the abovementioned Hebrew word "אדם" possesses the first letter as "א" which carries out the "greatest weight" (e.g., alike the "smallest babushka" shaping the shape of the whole "big babushka doll" (subsequently)! This "א" Hebrew letter receives the Gimatria value of "1" – but this "1" digit can be viewed as representing the highest value of the "fifty zero's" (e.g., "possessing the value of many "trillions" of times per second – and indeed appearing in all of the "larger babushka dolls", that is "appearing in all of the fifty zero's UF's) This "א" letter also represents symbolically "G-D" as it is also the beginning of the word "G-D" in Hebrew: "אלוקים"! Finally, this first letter "א" is also associated with the first (Secondary Seven HCD's) of "Good-Will" implying that this "אדם" word signifies a great degree of "Divine-Good-Will"! In contrast, the second letter in this word "ד" has a higher Gimatria value of "4" and is associated with the second (of the Seven Secondary HCD's) which represents the "gevurah" the spiritual left side of "judgement" and

"measurement" as signified by the "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir"... Interestingly the third letter is "ם" which has Gimatria numeric value of 40! and also represents the middle letter (or conjoining element) of the whole alphabet, with a special "spiritual" element of completion and wisdom (like Moses' 40 days on Mt. Sinai at which he received the Holy Torah (Bible)! Interestingly also the combination of the two last letters are "ד-ם" semantic meaning is the Hebrew word for "blood"; so a partial understanding of the "spiritual nature" of the Hebrew word for a human-being points at it signifying a strong "Divine-Goo-Will" together with a "less-strong" (but still significant) element of "judgement", "bodily", "measured" elements – and the need (or efforts) to "combine" between these apparently "disparate" influences, alongside a strong element of "Wisdom" and "Perfection"! Another interesting point to note is that those "five zero's" allocated by the UCP's computation to the "length of time" and "order" in which the UCP computes each of these five (Seven Secondary HCD's) it is suggested – represents the fact that for each of these "five-template letters" takes into account each of the other four remaining letters and it affected by them (for each word, e.g., with shorter or longer words possibly missing or having redundant repetitions in terms of their usage of those five-template letter structure of the UCP's fifty zero's computation)!

d) Four Physical Features UCP's Computation

The next phase or layer in the UCP's computation of all exhaustive objects involves the "translation" of the Seven Secondary HCD's & associated Gimatria's (e.g., of those five secondary HCD's) "spiritual nature" (described above) into the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time")! Hence, the UCP translates each one of the five mentioned HCD's "spiritual nature" (e.g., associated with its specific HCD nature as well as the abovementioned Gimatria analysis etc. elements) into the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"! As can be seen from the Diagram, once again the UCP's "allocation" of "four zero's" for each one of these five HCD's amounts in "twenty-zero's" is associated with this translation into the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mas" and "time")!

e) The UCP's "Infinite" – THCD's "Materialization" (6th Physical Feature: 47th-50th)

The concluding phase of the UCP's computation of each exhaustive spatial pixel and object in the whole universe relates to the UCP's "materialization" of each object based on the sixth HCD of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object 4 Physical Features", which summates and cumulates all of the abovementioned 20 zero's HCD's four corresponding physical features input into the four general physical features for each exhaustive object which the UCP computes! It is important to note that given the almost "Infinite complexity" of the necessary computation for every exhaustive object (in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s) – not only in terms of the four physical features, but also taking into consideration the other (abovementioned) facets of the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (e.g., including for instance the DEMP's need to "balance" and "correct" any "immoral action/s" made by any given individual human-being by producing the equivalent "negative situation" for that individual in order for him/her to make a sincere "teshuva"!?) Therefore, it is suggested that that the "Infinitude" of the UCP (itself) is necessary and involved in the Tenth "UCP's Infinite Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization! [47-50] in order to "materialize" any exhaustive object in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

One of the most fundamental changes that is brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is the key understanding that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s!?) This is simply due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four associated basic physical features of "space",

"energy", "mass" and "time") for each consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe (e.g., and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP)! As outlined previously, if the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), then there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s (or relationship/s) between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (at any consecutive UF's frame/s)! Moreover, since all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP ("in-between") any two consecutive UF's frame/s, therefore there also cannot exist any physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels across any two ("consecutive" or even "non-consecutive" UF's frame/s)!

This profound new realization discovered through "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm undermines and negates the most basic "material-causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm: Thus, for instance the basic "Big-Bang" Model associated with the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT was negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! According to the "Big-Bang" Model, the whole creation of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which created all of the suns, galaxies, planets, space, time, energy and mass in the universe!? But, since according to the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s), and the completely "dissolves" all such exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., back into itself!) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; therefore, there could not have existed any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising this (purely hypothetical) "Big-Bang" initial nuclear event! This is because there could not have existed any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising this (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event (at any single or multiple UF's frame/s)!? And (anyway) the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames, so that there cannot "develop" any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such (purely hypothetical initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its creation of any "suns", "galaxies", "space", "mass" or "energy" etc.!?

The "Infinite Nature" of the "Universal Consciousness Reality"!

We now come to a "pivotal transformative point" in Physics' basic understanding of the "Infinite" of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which underlies – and in fact even "manifests" as the entire physical universe, but yet "transcends" it (i.e. "Infinitely"!)? This is because when we begin examining each of the multifarious facets of the UCR's continuous computation- "dissolution"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") towards this UCP's/UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal State"; we immediately realize that the only manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR could continuously "compute", "dissolve", "sustain" and "develop" each and every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (simultaneously at the abovementioned incredible rate) – as "guided" by the UCP's/UCR's "Pre-planned Geulah Driven Blueprint Plan" is only based on this UCR's "Infinite Nature"!

In order to elucidate this "Infinite Nature" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, let's focus (separately) upon each of the various facets of this UCP/UCR "Consistency Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" various derived computations that are all necessary in order to allow this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR to compute the next subsequent UF's

frame/s (e.g., at this "incredible" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") First, let's focus on the UCP's "Consistency-Gimatria" based computation of all exhaustive objects in the universe – for every consecutive UF's frame/s! As delineated in previous articles, "G-D's Physics" new understanding of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") – specifically in terms of its four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") is derived from its "Gimatria" based computation of the five basic Hebrew letters' alphabetic-numeric value for each given object's Hebrew name (which alongside its "semantic" meaning, including "smaller" comprising semantic units or words contained within each given Hebrew name, as previously delineated); This is based upon the UCP's "infinitely complex" computation of those five basic (initially ordered) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) of "Goodwill" (חסד), "Conscious-Moral Development" (CMD) ("גבורה"), "UNCIA-RE-JRH & DEMP" ("אפירת"), "UCP's Computed Potential Object" ("נצח"), UCP's "Teshuva" ("הח") Gimatria based computation of the Four Physical Features (4PF'a):

Indeed, the UCP's/UCR's "Infinite"- e.g., even only in terms of its computation of those "Gimatria" based computation of the five-basic (initial HCD's) template letters of each given Hebrew name, which is being translated into the Four Physical Features computation of the specific value/s (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" for every exhaustive object in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") in utterly "incomprehensible"! When we take into account the greater "infinite" complexity of the this UCP's/UCR's computation the "UCP's Consistency" other facets of the "Conscious-Moral Development", "Dynamic Equilibrium Principle" (DEP) and "Geulah Driven Development" – we cannot but stand "perplexed", "astonished" (and indeed at a great "awe"), when we consider the utter "Infinite" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! This is because we begin realizing that when we look at any of the "infinite" atoms, quarks etc. comprising any single or multiple object in the universe, as well as the whole vast and "infinite" regions of the universe's expanse; and we take into account that just for the "static" "existence" and "sustenance" of the universe and all of its multifarious "infinite" exhaustive spatial pixels – it is necessary for this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR "Infinite" to compute each such exhaustive spatial pixel's "existence", "dissolution", "re-computation" (and "development") "simultaneously" at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ "!

But, when we "add" into this "infinite computational complexity" the fact that each of these exhaustive spatial pixels is also undergoing a "continuous development" originated by this singular UCP/UCR – for instance, through the UCP's "CMD" involves a "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the UCP that includes all of the universe's development – from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings: all assumed to have been computed and created in a mere "six days" (e.g., due to "G-D's Physics" Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) postulate and the universe's (otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", previously delineated); and the whole of the universe's development throughout its "history" – leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, which Humanity (and Science in now entering with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm), in which Science recognizes the singularity of the UCP/UCR, alongside its "intrinsic sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (which therefore affects and describes Humanity's "existence" and "behavior"!)? If we are just to "imagine" the "infinite complexity" of the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the whole development of the universe's history including its "macroscopic development" from "inanimate": matter, through "animate": plants, animals and

human-beings, and also its unique "specific objects' development" (pattern/s): Thus, for instance, we know that each unique "object", i.e., whether it be "inanimate matter" (of any specific type: atoms, subatomic particles, chemical compounds etc.) or even more so: "animate": plants, animals or human-beings possesses a unique characteristic for its "life-span development"! This means, that the UCP's "infinitely complex" computation of all "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings (e.g., "simultaneously" throughout Earth's different environments etc.) must "remember", "sustain", "dissolve" and "re-compute" and "develop" each particular Biological specie – based on its specific pattern of development across its full life-span, i.e., for an unfathomable number of Biological species and specific organisms (plants, animals or human-beings)!?

We must bear in mind that not only has the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm proven empirically to more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" (e.g., based upon the direct empirical validation of G-D's Physics above-mentioned two unique "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions!); but more fundamentally, the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm, e.g., assuming that everything in the universe (either at the "macroscopic" Relativistic level or at the "microscopic subatomic" levels) operates based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between a (finite) number of constituting material elements – was principally negated both based upon "G-D's Physics' New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, which asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same"- or "different"- UF's frame/s, e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this singular UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! In addition, "G-D's Physics" discovery of the (profound) "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) was (previously) shown (more fundamentally) to "principally negate" the very basic "Computational Structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! This is because this (novel) CDP indicated that underlying this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm there exists a basic "Self-Referential Computational System" Computational Structure which inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted through the CDP – i.e., instead leading to the inevitable recognition of the singular higher-ordered UCP which (alone) can simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s!

So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm must be strictly negated (e.g., as shown above and previously, due to "G-D's Physics' New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its novel CDP theoretical postulate) – in favor of the CDP's discovered (and empirically validated) identification of the singular higher-ordered UCP's continuous (simultaneous) "computation"- "dissolution"- "re-computation"- and "development" of all exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$!") This means that as we've begun seeing (above) the UCP's (simultaneous) computation of all "inanimate" and particularly "animate": plants, animals and human-beings involves an "Infinitude" of its computational complexity: to "remember", "sustain", "dissolve" and then "re-compute" and "develop" every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" values) for each individual plant, animal and human-being (simultaneously at this "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$!") In other words, since according to "G-D's Physics' New (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm, this singular higher-ordered UCP has "Pre-planned" the "Blueprint Plan" for the universe's entire development – e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals

and human-beings (i.e., as mentioned above and delineated previously occurring within the UCP's "Six Days Creation Model" due to the CHCF postulate and the CAGUARE's otherwise "unexplained" phenomenon!?) also "guides" the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, as can be seen from Figure 1 and Diagram 1; that the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s is dependent upon the "Three Initial Key" (TIK) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's), in which the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "Pre-planned" (from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, as mentioned above), which is also executed through the UCP's "Consistency" computation's (abovementioned) "Conscious-Moral Development"! This means that the UCP has to simultaneously compute "anew" for each consecutive UF's frame/s all "inanimate" matter's composition, i.e., once again: "remember", "sustain", "dissolve", "re-compute" and "develop" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, in terms of its four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"); and even exponentially more "infinitely complex" is the UCP's computation of every exhaustive "animate" object – based on its (abovementioned "Gimatria" alphabetic numeric translation into those Four basic Physical Features) and the "Infinitude" of the UCP's computation of every specific animate entity: particular plant (e.g., including the vast differences between an algae and say a huge Sequoia Tree!?), every exhaustive Biological animal species and every individual human-being – in terms of their particular "life-span development" characteristics at every "trillionth of a trillionth etc." (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!")

Indeed, our recognition of the utter "Infinitude" (capacities) of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR becomes even more apparent when we add into our understanding of the manner in which this UCP/UCR computes, sustains and develops the entire physical universe – the (abovementioned) "UCP's Consistency – DEMP" computation! This is because (as previously delineated) the UCP's DEMP essentially implies that (due to the UCP's "intrinsic-sublime" "All-Goodness" and "Moral" characteristic), the UCP's DEMP "balances" and "enhances" any given individual human-being's "moral-choice/s" – leading Humanity towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal", e.g., by "teaching" each individual human-being that it is truly "inseparable" from the "Oneness", "Peace", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" of this singular higher-ordered UCP! The UCP accomplishes this "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" through the DEMP's "balancing" of any individual human-being's selection of ("G-D forbid") "immoral action/s" towards another human-being instigated through the UCP's selection of an "equivalent-negative" situation in which that individual human being who ("G-D forbid") inflicted "pain"/"suffering" upon another individual human-being will have to experience the same "negative situation", so that he/she may make a sincere "teshuva", e.g., real "remorse" over the "wrong-doing" or "immoral action" they've done. Conversely, if any individual human-being have opted to "assist" or (otherwise) "act-morally" towards another individual human-being, then equally this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR will select an "equivalently-positive" situation, in which this "assisting" (moral-actioned) individual human-being will also have the "privilege" of experiencing such an "equivalently-positive" situation in which (most likely) that "other human-being" which he/she assisted will assist or bestow "goodness" upon himself/herself? As delineated previously, the manner in which this UCP's DEMP "operates" is based upon the existence of the UCP's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" comprising all possible "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" or each individual human-being (possessing a free moral choice)! This implies that this singular higher-ordered UCP has to compute for each individual human-being (at any "trillionth of a trillionth of a second etc.") the precise "situation" would allow that particular individual human-being to experience the "same" ("negative" or "positive" situation/s) in which that individual human-being ("G-D forbid") inflicted "pain/suffering" upon another human-being, so that this "negative-immoral situation" will lead that individual human-being to undertake a sincere "teshuva" (e.g., deep "remorse" and conscious

decision not to repeat any such "wrong-doing"! But, this means that this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR has to (simultaneously) compute for each of the over eight Billion individual human-beings (existing today) the DEMP's "balancing" of all of their previous "moral/immoral action/s" taken throughout their lives – while taking into consideration all of the "other human-beings" that were involved in their "moral/immoral action/s" at any point/s in time in their lives, and consequently compute (at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) every consecutive UF's frame/s that would "balance" any "immoral action/s" (e.g., acted upon "against" any specific individual human-being) by creating the same "equivalent negative" situation (e.g., most likely by "reversing" the situation so that the "injured other person" will "reproduce" the same "negative situation" so as to have the "injuring person" experience "G-D forbid" the same "negative-immoral" situation, or by "reinforcing" and "remunerating" any "positive moral-action" by any Individual human being (towards another human being) which necessitates the UCP's "reinforcement" or "remuneration" of this "positive-moral action" of that individual human being through the UCP's computation of all those "equivalent positive situation/s" in which the "good-moral actor" (human-being) is being "rewarded" (or "encouraged"/"remunerated") for his/her "right-moral choice"! In both cases, it is likely that the UCP's/UCR's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s will compute the "Infinitely complex" (abovementioned) "moral-balancing" for each individual human-being – i.e., as "coupled" with those particular individual human-being/s that he or she have acted in a "moral" or "immoral" manner at each "(minimal) time-point" along the course of their entire live/s, in order to compute (e.g., create) the "equivalently-positive/negative" situation (i.e., with those particular individual human-beings which that given individual human-being interacted (in a "positive" - or "negative" – moral action/s), in order to "morally-balance" or "morally enhance" each individual human-being (out of the over eight Billion individual human-beings living on the Planet Earth)!?)

If this is not "infinitely-complex"(enough), we must take into consideration the significance of the UCP's "teshuva" HCD's which allows for each (such) Individual human-being to make a sincere "teshuva" (as explained above) in which case the UCP will "avert" and "omit" the UCP's (preceding) "Computed Potential Object" ("צנח") – i.e., "equivalent negative situation" UF's situation, for each individual human-being (e.g., with his/her "coupled other human-being" towards which the "immoral action" was conducted, "G-D forbid"! Indeed, it is utterly "amazing" and "awe-inspiring" to realize the UCP's/UCR's "Infinitude" – having to compute not only the "infinitely complex" computation for each of Humanity's (eight Billion human-beings), but also to take into consideration within this "Infinitude" of the UCP's computation also the degree to which each of these (eight Billion individual human-beings) has undertaken a sincere "teshuva" (towards any single or multiple other individual human-beings), and the manner in which this "Infinitely complex" UCP's computation alters the UCP's "Computed Potential Object's" (e.g., potentially "equivalent negative situation" into an "equivalent positive situation") for the subsequent "Actual Computed Object" HCD's for each individual human being (out of the over eight Billion individual human-beings!) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm, due to this "Infinitude" complexity of the UCP's/UCR's simultaneous computation of the DEMP – for each of the over eight Billion Individual human-beings (living today on our Planet), the direct involvement of this "Infinitude UCR/UCP" in executing the actual "materialization" of the next subsequent UF's frame (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) at the tenth HCD's of the "UCP's Infinite Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization"!

"G-D's Physics" Computational Duality Principle's Negation of the MCR's SRCS Structure!

More fundamentally, one of "G-D's Physics" (profound) newly discovered

"Theoretical Postulates", called: the "Computational Duality Principle" has proven (i.e., in principle!) that the basic "Computational Structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is "flawed", e.g., comprising a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) which was shown to (inevitably) lead to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy", which are contradicted by these (apparently) SRCS Systems to carry out (successfully) the necessary computation in order to determine the outcome of that System; therefore pointing at the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP, which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$)

An important computational basis for this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm are two of its former Theoretical Postulates called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) and associated "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which state that it is not possible (in principle) for any two given computational elements ("x") and ("y") to determine (or "cause") the value/s of one of these elements (i.e., "y") – because such a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) would inevitably lead to both a "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted by that Computational System's proven (empirical) capacity to determine the given 'y' element's values: Specifically in the case of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (implicitly) assumed "Self-Referential Computational System" SRCS: it is assumed that it is only based on the direct physical interaction between certain (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" (DMDE) elements and their direct (or even indirect) physical interactions with all (possible) "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) of this SRCS System – that this SRCS System is able to compute whether these "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) would remain the "same" or "different" (e.g., "Not Uec")! Formally presented, this SRCS System of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm:

SRCS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Uec-aer" or "Not Uec-aer "

But, according to "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) such a SRCS System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" in the case of a "Negative" SRCS outcome, i.e., "SRCNS" – in which this SRCS System yields a "negative outcome":

SRCNS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Not Uec-aer"

In which it is assumed that this direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DMDE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- accelerated rate of expansion" (Uec) "cause" a "change" in this Uec-aer ("Not Uec-aer"); then this leads to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" – since this SRCNS System states that the universe possesses both the initial Uec-aer rate of expansion and also possesses a "Not Uec-aer" (increased) rate of expansion! Obviously, such SRCNS "logical-inconsistency" inevitably also leads to an intrinsic state of "computational-indeterminacy" because such a "material-causal" SRCS/SRCNS System cannot determine whether its initial Uec-aer or subsequent Not Uec-aer state of the universe's acceleration rate exists?! But, to the extent that we can validate "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER) – then this would negate the SRCNS assumed computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm!

Hence, the proposed "Critical-Prediction" of "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm that could differentiate it from the corresponding Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., regarding the "Big-Bang" Model and associated "Dark-Energy"/"Dark-Matter" should test for "G-d's Physics" predicted "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER), which coupled with the above CDP would unequivocally validate "G-d's

Physics" New ACC Paradigm's conception of the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s). The results are taken from a series of scientific studies indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP), This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNCS computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):

SRNCS: {DM/DE, Uec-er } ti → {"Not Uec-er"} ti+n

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE concepts) and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (Uec-ar) that "causes" the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?! But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNCS computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at ti : as Uec-er; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not Uec-er at ti+n ?! This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCS (SRNCS) computational System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be " Uec-er" (at ti) or " Not Uec-er" (at ti+n) ?! But, since according to the CDP we obtain clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c2 /h" = 1.36-50 sec!), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal timepoint"! Indeed, the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) conforms with "G-d's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Expansion Accelerated Rate" (UNCEAR) – which is further specified to occur during such (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" time-intervals as the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (JRH)!

As mentioned above, one of the significant theoretical postulates of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm is called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) which asserts that it is not possible, in principle, to compute any direct (or even indirect) relativistic or quantum physical relationship/s between any given "x" and "y" elements – from within their direct "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) assumed computational structure, but only from the higher-ordered singular "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP); This is because "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) reveals that this "problematic" ""Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) computational structure characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" that are intrinsic to this SRCS computational structure; But, since in all of those Relativistic or Quantum Systems, there exists robust empirical evidence that those Systems are capable of computing the outputted result of the System, therefore the CDP asserts that there must exist a singular high-

er-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" computing the various states and existence of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems! The most general representation of this CDP can be given as: Whenever there exists a SRCS System (of the computational structure) assuming that the whole computation is determined solely at the same "di1" computational level:

SRCS: {x, y} → "y" or "Not y"/di1 the possibility of SRNCS (e.g., "negative" "Not y" output): SRNCS {x, y} → "Not y"/di1 Inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency", since the "y" element seems to both "exist" and "not exist" at the same "di1" computational level?!

SRNCS {x, y} → "Not y"/di1 Such apparent "logical-inconsistency" also inevitably leads to an ensuing "computational indeterminacy", i.e., an apparent inability of such SRCS/SRNCS to determine whether the "y" element exists or "doesn't exist", e.g., denoting a different altered value for this "y" element?! But, since there exists specific empirical evidence for any of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems' capability to determine and output a particular "y" value, therefore this contradicts the Duality Principle's above proof that such an assumed SRCS/ SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – therefore the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (as postulated by "G-d's Physics" "Universal Computational Principle", e.g., thereby producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal-Frames", UF's at the incredible rate of "c2 /h" = 1.36-50 sec! comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal timepoint"); Hence, below is a detailing of the various examples and manifestations of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed SRCS (& SRNCS) Computational Systems – which are all constrained and in fact negated by "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, all pointing at the "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) asserted singular higher-ordered UCP (of "G-d's Physics New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm)! a). The "Big-Bang Model": The "Big-Bang" Model represents this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction/s between a certain "Nuclear Event" (NE) and a given "exhaustive components of the Universe" exhibiting a certain "expansion state" at (U-ec/es) that "causes" the universe's expansion state to "increase", e.g., that is, be "different" than the initial "expansion state", which can be represented as:

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es) /di1

Noteworthy is highlighting the implicit "material-causal" assumption of this "Big-Bang" Model's SRCS/SRNCS Computational System, e.g., whereby this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumes that it is solely based on this direct physical interaction between the NE and the initial state of the universe's expansion (U-ec/es) that this SRCS/SRNCS System is able to compute the different NOT (U-ec/es) state of the universe; Specifically that the entire SRCS/SRNCS computation exists at the same "di1" computational level of the SRCS! But, such a SRCS/SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to a "logical-inconsistency":

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es)/di1?!

This implies that the SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably also leads to an apparent "computational indeterminacy", e.g., an apparent inability of this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System to determine whether the universe will remain its initial (U-ec/e)s state or evolve into the latter " NOT (U-ec/es)"?! But, since there exists robust empirical evidence indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess

et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) indicates that there exists a Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – which actually increases "non-continuously" with time: "NOT (U-ec/es)!" Hence, according to the CDP, this Computational System cannot comprise the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's – but only the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational System" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec' of a series of "Universal Frames")! b). General Relativity Theory (GRT) "Einstein's Equations" Another (key) manifestation of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption is GRT's Einstein's Equations basic "material-causal" assumption: According to Einstein's Equations, the presence of certain "Massive Objects" (MO) and their direct physical interaction with "Space-Time" "causes" a change in the curvature level of this "Space-Time": SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1 But, once again, such a SRNCS output of the SRCS Computational System basic computational structure inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", i.e., in intrinsic inability of the SRCS(SRNCS) assumed Computational System to determine whether the initial STc or the subsequent "NOT STc" state of "Space-Time" should exist – since they're both intrinsic elements within the same SRCS/SRNCS "di1" computational level!

SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1

Therefore, once again the CDP points at the ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" of such a SRNCS Computational System, which cannot decide whether the resulting state of Relativistic System should remain at the initial STc state or undergo an additional curvature of Space-Time as in the more "curved SpaceTime" state, e.g., signified by "NOT STc"?! But, since the abovementioned clear empirical indication of the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) represents a "special-case" of GRT's Einstein's Equations, then this indicates that the Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (associated with Einstein's abovementioned SRCS/SRNCS assumed Computational System); Therefore, once again, the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features -of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", giving rise to an extremely rapid series of UF's frames; Indeed, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm was shown to offer an alternative computational account for the apparent "material-causal" "curvature of Space-Time by massive objects" – i.e., based on "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) novel computational definitions of the four basic physical features by this singular higher-ordered UCP, and the new "Universal Computational Formula" which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) between these four basic physical features of the universe:

S: (f_{x,y,z}{UF(i)} + ... f_{x,y,z}{UF(n)}) / h * n {UF's} such that: f_{x,y,z}{UF(n)} ≤ f_{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)}{UF's(i...n)}

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location

of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

E: (f_{x,y,z}{UF(i)} - ... f_{x,y,z}{UF(n)}) / c * n {UF's}

such that:

f_{x,y,z}{UF(n)} > f_{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)}{UF's(i...n)} wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

M: Σ[O_i{o-x,o-y,o-z} {UF(n)}] = O(i...n{o-x,o-y,o-z} {UF(i...n)}) / h * n{UF's(i...n)}

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

M: [O_i{x,y,z}UF's(i)] – O_n{x,y,z}UF's(i...n) ≤ n * h {UF's (i...n)}

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value. In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: Σ[O_i{o-x,o-y,o-z} {UF(n)}] ≠ O(i...n{o-x,o-y,o-z} {UF(i...n)}) / c * n{UF's(i...n)}

such that:

T: [O_i{x,y,z}UF's(i)] – O_n{x,y,z}UF's(i...n) ≤ c * h {UF's (i...n)}

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light. Universal Computational Formula (UCF): c). Quantum Mechanics "Material-Causal" Assumed Collapse of the Target's Probability Wave-Function: Another important manifestation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption which is challenged and negated by "G-d's Physics" New "Computational Duality Principle" is Quantum Mechanics' "material-causal" assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction between a given subatomic "probe" (P) element and a corresponding subatomic ("un-collapsed") "target's probability wave-function" (Tu-wf) – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse of the probability wave-funcation" into a single "complimentary" (space/energy or time/mass) value:

SRNCS: {P, Tu-wf} → "NOT Tu-wf"/di1

But, as stated above, according to the CDP such a SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computa-

tional-indeterminacy”:

SRNCS: {P, Tu-wf } → "NOT Tu-wf"/di1

Wherein this assumed SRNCS Computational System cannot decide whether the target element should exhibit its assumed "un-collapsed" probability wave function values or the single "complimentary" (space/energy or mass/time) "collapsed" value?! However, since we know empirically that any such QM System is capable of determining the "collapsed" single complimentary value of any given subatomic target element – therefore the CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe as an extremely rapid series of Universal Frames (UF's) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec"! As outlined and delineated extensively (previously) the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm expands, embeds and transcends the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's conception of QM's "single spatial-temporal" "particle", "multiple spatial-temporal" "wave" – and "exhaustive" "Universal Frames" (UF's) computational perspectives which are all embedded within the UCP's singular higher-ordered (integrated) "Universal Computational Formula" (outlined above).

The UCP's: SST, MST &EST Resolves the "Gravitational Enigma"!

Significantly, "G-D's Physics" discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, through its "extremely rapid" (" $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!") computation of the series of "Universal Frame/s" was also shown capable of resolving the basic "unresolved" "Gravitational Enigma" that is associated with "G-D's Physics" complete unification between GRT & QM!

Perhaps the key unresolved "enigma" in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "Gravitational Enigma" (GE), i.e.: Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can: a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm); Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and "independent") of the Standard Model's proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles' interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) based on the discovery of a New "G-d's Physics" Scientific Paradigm1-30;

The potential capacity of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!"), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Additionally, the UCP's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF's frame/s yields the UCP's novel

"computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency! According to this (new) G-D'S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the "mass" value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those "Framework" (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent") "Computational Dimensions": Such that the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" computations, as the "space" and "energy" values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF's); and "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations, as the "mass" and "time" values (across a given UF's series) (Figure 1):

FIGURE 2: UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

Intriguingly, these novel "G-D'S PHYSICS" UCP's "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an "Universal Computational Formula" (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

FIGURE 3: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Pxl (a..z)]

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} E * s \\ t \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} M * c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\frac{t * m}{s * e} = \frac{h}{c^2}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS" or G-D'S PHYSICS).

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm's potential resolution of the GE's first component – i.e., a) Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP's (in-depth) analysis of the (true) "computational basis" of the "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D'S PHYSICS's computational analysis, this "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" for the transmission of any "signal" (or even "information") across "space" and "time" – which seems to be "contradicted" by QM's "Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon", indicating that the measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the "complimentary" ("space/energy" or "mass/time") measurement of the other "entangled particle"?! But, according to the new CUT's Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and "resolution"- of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): "particle" of relativistic "object" (e.g., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): "wave" (e.g., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time) or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame", UF), across a series of UF's frames (Figure 4);

FIGURE 4: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

In order to advance towards demonstrating in what manner can this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm address and resolve the "second" (abovementioned) facet of the GE, we must now validate a unique "Critical Prediction" of this New G-D'S PHYSICS – as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT & QM!

"G-D's Physics" Complete Unification of GRT & QM, All Physical Features & Forces & Universal Developments!

Amongst the profound accomplishments of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm is its proven capacity to unify – not

only between GRT & QM, but also (for the first time in Physics!) between the Four basic Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass"); and between the Four basic "Forces of Nature" (as shown previously)! Indeed, this unique capacity of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm to completely unify between GRT & QM, as well as between the Four (basic) Physical Features and Forces – stems from its discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), who "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (e.g., four basic Physical Features for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! As shown previously, this unique capacity of the UCP to "simultaneously" compute these Four basic Physical Features arises from its usage of its three "Computational Dimensions" (e.g., "Framework" ["frame" or "object"] & "Consistency" ["consistent" or "inconsistent"]) – whose four possible combinations: i.e., "Frame-consistent": "space"; "Frame-inconsistent": "energy"; "Object-consistent": "mass"; and "Object-inconsistent": "time"! Thus, in truth, these apparently "Four (basic) Physical Features" are not really "separate" (or "independent") – but rather represent different "facets" of the same singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Principle" (or UCR) In much the same manner (as shown previously), this singular UCP/UCR also unifies the Four basic Forces of Nature, since all of these different "forces" merely represent those different "facets" of the UCP's computation (e.g., with all of the "different subatomic particles" or "forces" being derived from the UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF's) different possible "relationship/s" between the different possible values of these Four basic Physical Features, i.e., including each of these Physical Features' novel "computational definitions" according to "G-D's Physics" new UCP definitions (delineated previously).

But, the major "Paradigmatic Shift" or "fundamental metamorphosis" in our basic understanding of the physical universe brought about by this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is related to "G-D's Physics" new realization that the whole universe's existence (and development) has been "Pre-planned" and is being continuously "executed" (and "steered") by this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR towards the fulfillment of it's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the entire universe – in which Humanity will (all) recognize the singularity of this (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which will therefore also affect Humanity's general state and also every individual human-being's personal behavior)! Indeed, it is this singular higher-ordered "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan", which allows "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm to also completely unify between all the different "Physical", "Biological" and "Moral-Spiritual" facets of the universe's development! This is because according to this "Pre-Planned Blueprint Plan" for the universe's development: i.e., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, these various "Physical", "Biological" and "Moral-Spiritual" facets are completely integrated – and are (in fact) all being executed together by this (singular, higher-ordered) UCP's continuous "execution" of its "Pre-Planned Geulah Driven Plan" (as shown above and previously)! As can be (clearly) seen from the (above) UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Gimtaria Geulah-Driven Diagram" the UCP's "Consistency" HCD (continuously) computes these integrated: "Gimatria-Physical", "Conscious-Moral Development", "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP) and "Geulah-Driven Development" for each consecutive UF's frame/s' (exhaustive spatial pixels)!

G-D's Physics Revolutionizes Science Basic Conception of the Universe's Origination, Development & "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State!

Hence, our basic conception (and understanding) of the manner in which this entire physical universe is being continuously "originated"- "sustained"- and "evolved"- undergoes a major "metamorphosis" based on the discovery (and empirical validation) of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Caus-

al Computation" Scientific Paradigm! The physical universe could not have been created by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event – because the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the whole universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s! Moreover, based upon "G-D's Physics" (abovementioned) two profound "Computational Invariance" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates realization that (in fact) the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) represents only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which solely exists both "during" its extremely rapid (e.g., $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!) computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also (solely) exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., without the presence of any physical universe!) **whereas the entire physical universe merely represents a "computationally-variant" manifestation of this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality"!** In other words, according to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's (basic) understanding of the universe's (continuous) "origination" (by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" – so many "trillions" of times each second!?) "sustenance"- and "development"- (e.g., towards the UCP's/UCR's "Pre-planned" fulfillment of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State Goal" State of the universe) can only be explained based upon this singular UCP's/UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's) and associated "Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF) – rather than based upon (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any (single or multiple) UF's frame/s!

In this manner, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm challenges- and indeed negates- the basic Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) assumption which assumes that the whole existence of the entire physical universe (and every specific phenomenon within it) can be explained merely based on a series of "random" "material-causal" physical interactions (between a "finite" number of material or physical entities)! First, because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same or different UF's frame/s! Indeed, as indicated above, Science's basic conception of the origination-sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe was based on the (implicit) "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) assumption, wherein it is assumed that every physical (relativistic or quantum) phenomenon, effect, force, or entity (or composition) etc. can be explained merely based upon direct (or indirect) "material-causal" ("random") physical interactions between a finite set of material entities!? Hence, the universe was assumed to have been "created" or "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" ("random") nuclear event that created all of the suns, galaxies, matter and energy in the universe, and likewise the basic "physical laws" governing (and "dictating") the "dynamics" and "development" of the entire physical universe are assumed to result from General Relativity Theory's conception of direct physical interactions between certain "massive objects" and their curvature of "Space-Time", which in turn determine (or "cause") the "travelling-pathways" of these "massive" (and other "less-massive") objects; On the "Quantum" level, the Old MCR Model assumes that the physical properties of any (given) subatomic "target particle" – which is assumed to be "dispersed" along a "probability wave function", depends upon its direct physical interaction with another (corresponding) subatomic "probe" element, which then "causes" the "collapse" of this "probability wave-function" into a singular ("complimentary": "energy-space" or "time-mass") measured value of this "target particle"!? Consequently all the major "building-blocks" of Modern

Science are all based upon- or associated with- this basic MCR assumption: including the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event assumed to have created the universe, which also assumes that our own Earth planet is regarded as "randomly created" physical entity originated in this "Big-Bang" event and its consequent GRT's assumed MCR dynamics; in this regards, Earth's and associated Humanity's "significance" and "role" in the overall scheme of the universe's creation and evolution is "minimal" and (almost) "insignificant"!? Specifically, Humanity's origination (and significance) as part of the universe's assumed MCR's origination and development – is also assumed to have been caused as part of "Darwin's Natural Selection Process" (DNSP) Evolutionary Theory which assumes that all Biological organisms and species have been "caused" by a "random" "Natural Selection Process" which depends upon the direct "material-causal" physical interactions between: a) Genetically-Mutated Organisms" (GMO) vs. "Non-Genetically Mutated Organisms" (NGMO) which are therefore "differentially compatible" to a given set of "Environmental Factors", i.e., with those GMO's becoming more "Environmentally Compatible" (EC) than the NGMO that are "Environmentally Incompatible" (EIC)!? This assumed Old MCR's Paradigm's assumed DNSP "mechanism" is assumed to have "caused" the evolution of all Biological Species on Planet Earth – including the "random" development of (our own) human-being's ("Homo-sapiens") species, which is assumed to have appeared "relatively late" (around 300,000 years ago), based on DNSP "random" evolutionary process... So, in essence, the Old MCR Scientific Paradigm assumes that the whole physical universe was created "randomly" as a result of an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and is evolving "randomly" based on direct (or indirect) MCR's processes that include GRT's (abovementioned) physical dynamics (e.g., of "massive objects" "curvature" of Space-Time etc.) and a completely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" (DM/DE) concepts assumed to "cause" the accelerated expansion of the universe (also based upon the same MCR basic assumption); Moreover, according to this Old Scientific Paradigm's MCR GRT's understanding, the whole universe (including our own Planet Earth) is "destined" to "dissipate" with an eventual "extinguishing" of all suns and energy etc. and ever-growing expansion and "dissipation" of the universe... Earth's and Humanity's (own) "existence", "role" and "significance" is therefore considered as "minimal" or "insignificant" – having being "created" based on a completely "random" (initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event, followed by a completely "random" DNSP's Evolutionary creation of our own Homo sapiens specie... Earth's own assumed "orbiting" around the Sun at one of the "distant" loci in the universe also reflects the "random" and "insignificant" role or Earth and Humanity in the overall scheme of the universe's (assumed) "random" creation and evolution...

But, according to the New (empirically proven) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Physics this Old MCR Paradigm has been strictly "challenged" and (in fact) clearly negated! This is because based on this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the singular higher-ordered UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe, "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s) negates the very possibility of the existence of any such "material-causal" physical relationships! Therefore, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) such "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame! Hence, the discovery of "G-D's Physics" (profound) New Scientific Paradigm, and its (unequivocal) empirical validation (e.g., based on two of its unique "Critical Predictions" – as more accurate than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal-Random" (MCR) Paradigm's GRT's & QM predictions!) have been shown to challenge and negate some of the most basic MCR assumptions of the Old Paradigm!

The universe could not have been "created" (or "caused") by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event – since there could not have occurred any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the "first"- "second"- or even "trillionth" etc. UF's frame/s, i.e., including between this initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its assumed "creation" of the various suns, galaxies, energy and mass in the universe! Moreover, since all of the universe's multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, therefore the cannot exist any physical "effect" or even "force" – existing "across" any two ("consecutive" or even "non-consecutive") UF's frame/s! Therefore also, the basic MCR assumptions underlying both GRT and QM are (strictly) negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! There cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between (certain) "massive" objects and their "curvature of Space-Time", nor between this (assumed) "curved Space-Time" and its "causing" (or "determination") of those "massive"- or other "less-massive" objects, (i.e., either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s)! Likewise, GRT's Einstein's Equations' other (two) "Exceptional Expulsive Effects" – of the "Cosmological Constant" and "Dark Matter/Dark-Energy" (DM/DE) are principally negated, since they are also based upon this Old MCR fundamental assumption: wherein, it is assumed that it is the direct "material-causal" physical interaction between those (purely hypothetical) concepts of the "Cosmological Constant" and the physical universe (e.g., or certain "galactic elements etc. within it) that "cause" the accelerated expansion of the universe (or specific "galactic elements" within it)! But, as indicated (above and previously), "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm strictly negates the very possibility of the existence of any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s)!

Indeed, as shown above (and previously), "G-D's Physics" profound discovery of the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) principally negated the basic "Self-Referential Computational System" (SROCS) computational structure of each of these Old Paradigm's Relativistic or Quantum (or even the above mentioned DNSP's) MCR's Systems; This is because such SRCS Computational System structure inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – which are negated by the proven empirical capacity of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems to computes the universe's accelerated rate of expansion, or measured (complimentary) value of any given subatomic "target" element! Therefore, "G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) points at the existence of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s (thereby producing the extremely rapid series of UF's frames comprising the entire physical universe!) This principle negation of the basic MCR (SRCS computational structure) of the Old Paradigm's (Relativistic and Quantum) Models is made even more apparent based on the above mentioned "G-D's Physics" two additional (profound) "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) – which essentially teach us that since only this singular higher-ordered UCP remains "constant" "continuous" and "invariant" both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s and also solely remains (without the presence of the universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s) therefore there only truly exists one singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which both manifests" as the entire physical universe "during" each consecutive UF's frame, and remains (solely) without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

Hence, the discovery and empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (alongside its two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates) negated the Old MCR Paradigm of GRT & QM (as well as the older Newtonian Mechanics and Galilean conceptions) – instead pointing at the singularity of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCR or UCP)! And as shown above (and previously), we realize that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR continuously computes- "dissolves"- re-computes- and evolves- every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is based on its Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's) and associated "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which point at the "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR to develop the whole universe from its "inanimate": matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards fulfilling its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe – in which Humanity recognizes this singularity of the UCP/UCR, alongside its unique "sublime" characteristics, e.g. of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony" (and lives accordingly)! Indeed, one of the two (above mentioned) unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm predicted the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) associated with "G-D's Physics" postulated "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" occurring at the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) two days' special time interval (in which Millions of Jews from all over the world focus on this singular UCR, or "G-D"!), which brings about an increase in the universe's expansion rate (every year); was empirically validated (indirectly) based on the (otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE)! Hence, it seems that "G-D's Physics" postulated "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – associated with our planet Earth serves as the "Functional Epi-center" of the entire physical universe (as shown above and previously)!

Thus, Science (and Humanity) reach a "pivotal turning point" in which Humanity realizes that the universe was not created "randomly" or "purposelessly", and is not governed by mere "Material-Causal-Random" physical interactions (e.g., either at the "Relativistic" or "Quantum" levels), but has rather been (precisely) "Pre-planned" by the sole reality of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) in order to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (e.g., postulated above to have occurred within six days, due to the centrality of this CHCF in allowing the UNCIARE-JRH from the universe's beginning!) towards fulfilling the Universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe, which Humanity is now "entering" – with Science's acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

References

1. Bentwich, J. (2012a) "Harmonizing Quantum Mechanics and Relativity Theory". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, Intech (ISBN 979-953-307-377-3), Chapter 22, pp. 515-550.
2. Bentwich, J. (2012b) "Theoretical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory". Theoretical Concepts of Quantum Mechanics, (ISBN 979-953-307-3773), Chapter 23, pp. 551-598.
3. Bentwich, J. (2013b). "The Theoretical Ramifications of the Computational Unified Field Theory". Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7), Chapter 28, pp. 671-882.
4. Bentwich, J. (2013c). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): A Candidate Theory of Everything. Advances in Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-1089-7) Chapter 18, pp. 395-436.
5. Bentwich, J. (2015). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): A Candidate 'Theory of Everything'. Selected Topics in Application of Quantum Mechanics (ISBN 978-953-51-2126-8) Chapter 6.

6. Bentwich, J. (2014) What if Einstein was Right? Amazon Kindle Book Store.
7. Bentwich, J. (2015). On the Geometry of Space, Time, Energy, and Mass: Empirical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory. Unified Field Mechanics: Natural Science Beyond the Veil of Spacetime (Proceedings of VIGIER IX Conference, Morgan State University, USA, 16-19 November 2014).
8. Bentwich, J. (2016) The 'Computational Unified Field Theory': A Paradigmatic Shift. Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics.
9. Bentwich, J. (2017a) The Computational Unified Field Theory: Could 'Dark Matter' & 'Dark Energy' be "Superfluous"? SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
10. Bentwich, J. (2017b) The Computational Unified Field Theory: Explaining the Universe from "Without". SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
11. Bentwich, J. (2017e). Can the 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT) Challenge the Basic Laws of Conservation? SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
12. Bentwich, J. (2017f). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): Time "Reversal" May be Possible. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
13. Bentwich, J. (2017g). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Transcends Relativity's Speed of Light Constraint. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics, Special Issue.
14. Bentwich, J. (2017h). The Computational Unified Field Theory's New Physics: Transcending Space, Time and Causality. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
15. Bentwich, J. (2017i). A "Supra-Spatial-Temporal Universal Consciousness Reality". Research & Reviews: Journal of Pure & Applied Physics, Special Issue: The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT)- A Paradigmatic Shift in 21st Century Physics.
16. Bentwich, J. (2017j). A New Science: An Infinite Omniscient Dynamic-Equilibrium Universal Consciousness Reality. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
17. Bentwich, J. (2017k). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Challenges Darwin's 'Natural Selection Principle'! SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
18. Bentwich, J. (2017l). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Challenges the Second Law of Thermodynamics. SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
19. Bentwich, J. (2017m). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): An Empirical & Mathematical Validation of the 'Computational Unified Field Theory'; SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
20. Bentwich, J. (2017n). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) New Science; SciFed Journal of Quantum Physics Special Issue.
21. Bentwich, J. (2018a). Review: The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) New Universe: The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
22. Bentwich, J. (2018b). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT): What is "Time"? The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
23. Bentwich, J. (2018c). The Universal Consciousness Reality's Camouflage: The Physical Universe! The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
24. Bentwich, J. (2018d). The Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) Epilogue: Can Human Consciousness Affect the Cosmos? The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
25. Bentwich, J. (2018e). Testing the Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) Differential-Critical Predictions: The Higgs-Boson Particle May Not Exist Continuously! The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
26. Bentwich, J. (2018f). The Double-Faceted Universal Consciousness Reality: A Theoretical Review. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
27. Bentwich, J. (2018g). Letter to the Editor: Dark Matter May Not Exist. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
28. Bentwich, J. (2018h). The Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) Epilogue: Possible Reversal of the Arrow of Time and Abolishment of Death. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
29. Bentwich, J. (2019a). The Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) New Universe. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
30. Bentwich, J. (2019b). The Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) Goes Beyond the 'Standard Model': "G-d's Physics"?. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 18 (8-A), Special Issue.
31. Bentwich, J. (2019c). A Call for Cosmologists & Experimental Physicists: Empirical Validation of the 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT) New Paradigm through "Time-Sensitive" Astronomical and Subatomic Measurements. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
32. Bentwich, J. (2019d). The 'Computational Unified Field Theory' (CUFT): Redefining Mass, Gravity & the Physical Universe. The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
33. Bentwich, J. (2019d). Astronomical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory (CUFT) "Critical Prediction" & Resolution of the "Universe's Accelerated Expansion Rate Enigma" (UAERE). The Global Journal of Science Frontier Research, Vol. 19 (6), Special Issue.
34. Bentwich, J. (2019e) Urgent Call for Empirical Validation of the Computational Unified Field Theory's (CUFT) New 21st Century 'A-Causal Computation' (ACC) Paradigm. Acta Scientific Applied Physics, Volume 1(1).
35. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2020a). 'G-d's Physics' (CUFT) New "Atom" & Purposeful Universe! Advances in Theoretical & Computational Physics. Volume 3 (2), p. 50-58.
36. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2020b). An Urgent Need for "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm's Empirical Validation. Advances in Theoretical & Computational Physics. Volume 3 (2), p. 59-65.
37. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021). "G-d's Physics: A New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century. iUniverse. ISBN 9781532090370.
38. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021a). "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm: From "Law" to "Mercy"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
39. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021b). "G-d's Physics": From Arbitrary Physical & Biological "Evolution" Towards A Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) Directed Morally-Perfected ("Geulah") Universe! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
40. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021c). "G-d's Physics": On the True Nature of "Dark-Energy" & "Dark-Matter". In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
41. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021d). The New "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Paradigm: A Morally Perfected ("Geulah h ") Directed New Physical Universe! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).

43. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021e). "G-d's Physics": It's "Time" for "Geulah h"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
44. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021f). "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) New Physics Paradigm: "Miracles" Can Happen!?. In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
45. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021g). "G-d's Physics" New 21st Century Paradigm: A Complete Integration of "Space" & "Energy", "Mass" & "Time"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
46. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021h). "G-d's Physics": Complete Unification of the Four Basic Forces of Nature & "Geulah h"! In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
47. Bentovish (Bentwich), J. (2021i). Fulfilling Einstein's Quest: "G-d's Physics" New Twenty-First Century's Paradigm's Multi-Level Computational Universe. In World Journal of Pharmaceutical & Medical Research, Special Issue: "G-d's Physics New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm: Empirical & Theoretical Ramifications (In Press).
48. Dahia, F.; Lemos, A.S. (2016). "Is the proton radius puzzle evidence of extra dimensions?". European Physical Journal. 76 (8): 435. arXiv:1509.08735. Bibcode:2016EPJC...76..435D. doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-016-4266-7. S2CID 118672005
49. Karr, J.; Hilico, L. (2012). "Why three-body physics does not solve the proton-radius puzzle". Physical Review Letters. 109 (10): 103401. arXiv:1205.0633. Bibcode:2012PhRvL.109j3401K. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.109.103401. PMID 23005286. S2CID 12752418
50. Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962). The Structure of Scientific Revolutions (1st ed.). University of Chicago Press. pp. 172. LCCN 62019621
51. Lestone, J.P. (4 October 2017). Muonic atom Lamb shift via simple means (Report). Los Alamos Report. Los Alamos National Laboratory. LA-UR-17-29148.
52. Liu Y, McKeen D, Miller GA (2016). "Electrophobic Scalar Boson and Muonic Puzzles". Physical Review Letters. 117 (10): 101801. arXiv:1605.04612. Bibcode:2016PhRvL.117j1801L. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.101801. PMID 27636468. S2CID 20961
53. Onofrio, R. (2013). "Proton radius puzzle and quantum gravity at the Fermi scale". EPL. 104 (2): 20002. arXiv:1312.3469. Bibcode:2013EL....10420002O. doi:10.1209/0295-5075/104/20002. S2CID 119243594
54. Pohl R, Antognini A, Nez F, Amaro FD, Biraben F, et al. (July 2010). "The size of the proton" (PDF). Nature. 466 (7303): 213–216. Bibcode:2010Natur.466..213P. doi:10.1038/nature09250. PMID 20613837. S2CID 4424731.
55. Pohl R, et al. (2016a). "Laser spectroscopy of muonic deuterium". Science. 353 (6300): 669–673. Bibcode:2016Sci...353..669P. doi:10.1126/science.aaf2468. hdl:10316/80061. PMID 27516595. S2CID 206647315.
56. Pohl R, et al. (16 September 2016b) "Proton-radius puzzle deepens". CERN Courier. After our first study came out in 2010, I was afraid some veteran physicist would get in touch with us and point out our great blunder. But the years have passed, and so far nothing of the kind has happened.
57. Zyga, Lisa (November 26, 2013). "Proton radius puzzle may be solved by quantum gravity". Phys.org. Retrieved September 2, 2016.
58. Riess A. G., Casertano S., Yuan W. et al (2018a). Is there any measurable redshift dependence on the SN Ia absolute magnitude? ApJ 861 126 33.
59. Shajib A. J., Birrer S., Treu T. et al (2020). STRIDES: a 3.9 per cent measurement of the Hubble constant from the strong lens system DES J0408-5354. MNRAS 494 6072 34.
60. Scolnic D., Rest A., Riess A. et al (2014). Systematic Uncertainties Associated with the Cosmological Analysis of the First PAN-STARRS1 Type Ia Supernova Sample. ApJ 795 45 35.
61. Wong K. C., Suyu S. H., Chen G. C. F. et al (2020). H0LiCOW – XIII. A 2.4 per cent measurement of H0 from lensed quasars: 5.3 σ tension between early- and late Universe probes. MNRAS 498 1420

Cite this article: Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich) (2024) G-D's Physics Revolutionizes Science's Basic Conception of the Universe's Origination, Development & "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! Research & Reviews Journal of Modern Physics. **"G-D'S PHYSICS" NEW TWENTY-FIRST CENTURY SCIENTIFIC PARADIGM Special Issue:** 300-329.

Copyright: ©2023 Jehonathan Bentovish (Bentwich). This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.